

Comparison and evaluation of sampling and eDNA metabarcoding protocols to assess soil biodiversity in Belgian LUCAS Biopoints

EJP Soil WP6. Task 6.3: Double sampling exercise, part B. Soil Biodiversity assessment

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Abstract

Environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding is emerging as a novel tool for monitoring soil biodiversity. Soil biodiversity, critical to soil health and ecosystem services, is currently under-monitored due to the lack of standardized and efficient methods. We evaluated whether refinements to sampling protocols (for soil invertebrates and Fungi) and molecular protocols (for soil invertebrates) could enhance the detection and monitoring of soil biodiversity. Comparing the 2018 LUCAS soil biodiversity protocol with newly developed national methods, we tested sampling and sequencing surface layers (0-10 cm and forest floor) versus deeper layers, larger soil sample sizes for DNA-extraction, taking more subsamples for composite soil samples, and alternative primer sets across 9 Belgian Biopoints included in the LUCAS 2022 survey. We show that the choice of sampling protocol significantly influences soil biodiversity assessments. The results show that, based on eDNA, we are able to detect significantly more species when sampling and sequencing the upper soil layers separately (including the forest floor layer), while the diversity in the 10–30 cm soil layer is insufficient for annelids and arthropods to serve as indicators of ecological changes. Collembola and Arthropoda richness and diversity generally increased towards less intensely managed soils, when using the national (Cmon), and to a lesser extent the European (LUCAS) sampling protocols, with the highest values recorded in forests. In contrast, sampling and sequencing the 10-30 cm layer failed to capture such a pattern. Overall, the analyses suggest that soil depth has a greater influence on the soil invertebrate diversity captured than sampling intensity, and that the highest diversity is recovered when surface sampling (0–10 cm topsoil and forest floor) is combined with a greater number of subsamples (16 compared to 5 in LUCAS) and a larger sampled area. The most pronounced differences between sampling protocols were observed in grasslands for Annelida, and in forests for Collembola, Arthropoda, and Fungi. Additionally, comparison of the universal eukaryotic primers (18S) with primer sets tailored to important soil invertebrate groups, showed that universal 18S primers provide limited resolution for Collembola and Annelida, making them less suitable for accurately assessing the diversity of these groups as a response variable in monitoring ecological changes and biological soil health. With refinement and standardization, eDNA metabarcoding, combined with optimized sampling protocols, could become a powerful and efficient tool for monitoring soil biodiversity in European soils.

Recommendations for management and/or policy

1. Focus on surface sampling (0-10 cm and forest floor)

The results show that, based on eDNA, we are able to detect significantly more species when sampling and sequencing the upper soil layers separately (including the forest floor layer), while the diversity in the 10–30 cm soil layer is insufficient for annelids and arthropods to serve as indicators of ecological changes. Enhancing monitoring protocols to prioritize these layers will provide the data necessary to establish and utilize soil biodiversity indicators for monitoring ecological changes and soil health. We therefore recommend that also the LUCAS protocol samples the 0-10 cm depth instead of 0-30 cm layer in Biopoints.

2. Use specific primer sets for indicator taxa

The amplification bias and limited taxonomic resolution of universal eukaryotic primers highlights the need for primer sets tailored to key soil invertebrate groups, such as earthworms, potworms, and springtails. Improved molecular tools will enable accurate inclusion of these groups in soil biodiversity assessments, facilitating the identification of policy-relevant indicators of soil health.

3. Use optimized DNA-extraction methods

The results suggest that we are able to detect more taxa when using DNA-extraction methods that can use a larger amount of starting material (soil). Following the LUCAS protocol for DNA-extraction, 0.25 g of soil is used, which is relevant for microorganisms, but not representative enough for meso- and macrofauna, where at least 15 g is needed.

4. Increase sampling intensity and sampling area

The results suggest that we are able to detect more species when more subsamples are taken over a larger area to make the composite soil sample. Detecting a greater number of species provides a larger, more robust, and more representative dataset, which improves the ability to identify ecological patterns and trends. With a limited number of detected species, accurately discerning such patterns becomes significantly more challenging. Including a larger amount of

subsamples over a larger area than currently prescribed in the LUCAS protocol, will improve the consistency and comparability of datasets, enabling more robust and evidence-based policy development.

5. **Consider soil invertebrate groups as soil health indicators**

We state our opinion that for evaluating soil biological quality using eDNA metabarcoding, soil invertebrate groups should be considered alongside microbial communities when developing biotic indices for specific land-use types. While microorganisms often respond rapidly to various environmental changes, they also exhibit high spatial variability at fine scales, potentially reflecting microhabitat conditions rather than broader ecosystem trends. In contrast, soil invertebrates integrate longer-term ecological shifts and tend to have larger spatial distributions, making them valuable indicators of cumulative environmental impacts. However, both groups offer complementary insights, and the choice of indicators should align with specific ecological and management objectives.

Vertaalslag Vlaanderen

De groeiende erkenning van het belang van bodembiodiversiteit voor ecosystemen en ecosysteemdiensten heeft geleid tot de ontwikkeling van het Europese bodembeleid, zoals de bodemstrategie voor 2030 (gezonde bodems tegen 2050) en het voorstel voor de bodemmonitoringswet, waardoor de noodzaak voor een uitgekiende monitoring van bodembiodiversiteit, met robuuste referentiewaarden, monitoringsinstrumenten, indicatoren en haalbare doelen essentieel wordt. Kennishiaten ivm de karakterisatie, kwantificatie en monitoring van bodembiodiversiteit verhinderen echter de ontwikkeling van effectieve protocollen voor beleidsrelevante monitoring. De opkomende techniek van eDNA-metabarcoding biedt echter een veelbelovende oplossing door uitgebreide en efficiënte biodiversiteit monitoring mogelijk te maken over diverse functionele groepen heen. De eDNA-metabarcoding protocollen voor het meten van bodembiodiversiteit van het Joint Research Centre (JRC) voor de 2018 LUCAS meetcampagne breidden de Europese bodemmonitoring uit en voegen zowel micro- als macro-organismen toe met behulp van

een gestandaardiseerde DNA-extractiemethode en vier primer-sets. Hun resultaten wijzen echter onverwacht in de richting van een hogere biodiversiteit in akkerbodems in vergelijking met bossen of minder intensief beheerde graslanden, wat eerdere bevindingen op basis van traditionele methoden, die een daling van biodiversiteit laten zien bij toenemende landgebruiksintensiteit, tegenspreekt. Deze studie vergelijkt de LUCAS-protocollen met nieuw ontwikkelde nationale protocollen, gebruikmakend van eDNA-metabarcoding om bodembiodiversiteit te evalueren op 9 LUCAS Bioproefvlakken (Biopoints) in België. Er werd getest of het extraheren van DNA uit enkel de bovenste 10 cm van de bodem, het extraheren van DNA uit een grotere hoeveelheid bodem, het combineren van meer substalen voor het maken van het bodem mengstaal, en het gebruik van extra primer-sets de karakterisatie en kwantificatie van bodembiodiversiteit verbetert. Aangezien het merendeel van het wetenschappelijk eDNA gebaseerd bodemonderzoek tot nu toe gericht is op micro-organismen, vereist de methodologie voor de studie van andere bodemorganismen, zoals regenwormen, potwormen, insecten en springstaarten een verdere verbetering. Het optimaliseren van staalname- en analyseprotocollen is essentieel om een beter inzicht te krijgen in de biodiversiteit van de Vlaamse en Europese bodemecosystemen en het onderbouwen van indicatoren voor bodemgezondheid. In deze studie laten we zien dat universele eukaryotische primers slechts een beperkt aantal reads en een lage taxonomische resolutie opleveren voor Annelida (ringwormen) en Collembola (springstaartjes). Dit maakt deze primers minder geschikt voor het bepalen van de diversiteit van deze groepen als indicatoren voor ecologische veranderingen. Vergelijkingen tussen verschillende DNA-extractiemethoden tonen aan dat het extraheren van DNA uit een grotere hoeveelheid bodem (~20 g) aanzienlijk beter presteert dan de standaard Powersoil Pro-methode obv ~0.25 g, met de identificatie van 30 extra genera binnen Collembola, Annelida en Arthropoda (geleedpotigen). Een tweede conclusie is dat de keuze van het staalname protocol een significante invloed lijkt te hebben op het meten van bepaalde indicatoren zoals de soortenrijkdom van regenwormen, potwormen, springstaartjes, en arthropoden. Bij het analyseren van de 0-10 cm toplaag (conform Cmon protocol) werd het hoogste aantal soorten geïdentificeerd, met statistisch significante verschillen in vergelijking met de 0-30 cm toplaag bemonsterd volgens het LUCAS staalname protocol. De meest opvallende verschillen op basis van deze staalname protocollen werden waargenomen in graslanden en een Brussels park voor Annelida, en in bossen voor Collembola en Arthropoda. Verticale bodemstratificatie had het sterkste effect op de relatieve soortenrijkdom van locaties, wat wijst op detectie van verschillende soorten in de 0-10 vs 10-30 cm laag. Voor bossen werd bovendien tot 50% van

de biodiversiteit enkel gedetecteerd in de strooisellaag, en tot maar liefst 81% enkel in de strooisellaag en/of 0-10 cm laag, terwijl de 10-30 cm laag slechts een beperkte bijdrage leverde, met maximaal 6% van de biodiversiteit die uitsluitend in deze laag werd gedetecteerd. Voor Collembola en Arthropoda namen soortenrijkdom en diversiteit over het algemeen toe naarmate de landgebruiksintensiteit afnam op basis van de analyse van 0-10 cm stalen, en in iets mindere mate konden we dit patroon ook vaststellen op basis van de LUCAS-stalen. De hoogste waarden werden hierbij geregistreerd in bossen. De analyses van de 10-30 cm laag daarentegen detecteerden dit patroon niet: de soortenrijkdom was vergelijkbaar tussen alle landgebruikstypes, terwijl de diversiteit zelfs afnam in minder intensief beheerde ecosystemen met de hoogste waarden in akkers. Over het algemeen wijzen de resultaten erop dat diepte een grotere invloed heeft op de biodiversiteit van bodemfauna dan het aantal substalen dat is genomen om het mengstaal te maken, en dat de combinatie van oppervlakkige bemonstering (0-10 cm laag) met een hoger aantal substalen (16 in plaats van 5 volgens LUCAS protocol) de hoogste biodiversiteit detecteert. In bossen lijkt de staalname van de strooisellaag voor eDNA-metabarcoding bijzonder nuttig en informatief.

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Glossary

Term	Definition
Annelida	Large Phylum that comprises the segmented worms, including the dominant soil annelids: earthworms and potworms.
Arthropoda	Large Phylum of invertebrate animals that includes e.g. insects and spiders
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variant
Collembola	Springtails, the largest of the three lineages of modern hexapods that are no longer considered insects
CLR	Centered log-ratio transformation that expresses read counts per taxon as the log of their ratio to the geometric mean of read counts across all taxa in a sample.
eDNA	Environmental DNA
Forest floor	Uppermost layer of the forest soil consisting of dead and decomposing organic matter
INBO_0_10	Refers to the Cmon 0-10 cm sampling protocol
INBO_10_30	Refers to the Cmon 10-30 cm sampling protocol
LUCAS	Refers to the sampling protocol of the LUCAS soil survey, where the 0-30 cm soil layer is sampled
Metabarcoding	A high-throughput DNA sequencing technique used to identify multiple species from environmental or bulk samples based on genetic markers.
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
Sampling intensity	Amount of subsamples used to make the composite soil sample
Soil-dwelling	Living primarily within the soil
Soil-surface	Living primarily on the soil surface or in the forest floor

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of the vital role that soil biodiversity plays in the overall health and functioning of ecosystems, along with its direct impact on human well-being (Banerjee & Van Der Heijden, 2023; Brevik *et al.*, 2020; Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.*, 2020; Wagg *et al.*, 2019). This has led to the development of several (novel) policies dedicated to safeguarding soil biodiversity and its functions in the European Union, such as the EU Biodiversity and Soil Strategies for 2030 and the European Soil Monitoring Law (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2020, 2021; Köninger *et al.*, 2022). In order to facilitate the implementation of such policies, there is a need for a strong baseline, robust monitoring instruments, reliable indicators and ambitious yet achievable targets (Guerra *et al.*, 2021; Stone *et al.*, 2016; Zeiss *et al.*, 2022). However, critical knowledge gaps regarding soil diversity and health currently hinder the development of successful monitoring protocols. A particular area of concern is the characterization, quantification, and monitoring of soil biodiversity (Guerra *et al.*, 2021). Soil, as a habitat, accommodates a rich variety of microorganisms, encompassing bacteria, archaea, fungi, protists, and diverse invertebrate species including nematodes, earthworms and arthropods (Wagg *et al.*, 2014). Due to this vast diversity of life in soil, the development of indicators with high relevance for impact assessment studies and biodiversity monitoring in function of policy design, requires a broad coverage of the soil biome.

To acquire such coverage within a reasonable timeframe, the emerging technique of eDNA metabarcoding might be a viable option for capturing as much biodiversity as possible (Blackman *et al.*, 2024; Thomsen & Willerslev, 2015). Metabarcoding is the process of taxonomically identifying multiple species through DNA analysis, typically focusing on specific areas of the (mito)genome (e.g. the 18S rRNA or ITS region). When DNA is extracted directly from an environmental sample, without the prior isolation of specific target organisms, we refer to it as environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding (Deiner *et al.*, 2017; Ruppert *et al.*, 2019; Taberlet *et al.*, 2012a). eDNA metabarcoding has been demonstrated as a powerful technique to survey aquatic biodiversity (Deiner *et al.*, 2017; Keck *et al.*, 2022; Ruppert *et al.*, 2019; Serrana *et al.*, 2019), soil microbial biodiversity (Giachello *et al.*, 2023; Romero *et al.*, 2024; Van Der Heyde *et al.*, 2022), and soil invertebrate biodiversity (Arribas *et al.*, 2021; Calderón-Sanou *et al.*, 2022; Hermans *et al.*, 2022; Leclerc *et al.*, 2023; Lilja *et al.*, 2023; Llanos *et al.*, 2023; Oliverio *et al.*, 2018; Porter *et al.*, 2019; Rimmel *et al.*, 2024). In addition to identifying taxonomic diversity, genetic methods

can also be used to develop indicators for various land-use types (e.g. grassland, cropland), specific soil functions (e.g. organic matter and nutrient turnovers, water infiltration) or soil threats (e.g. soil contamination, salinisation, compaction). Furthermore, indicators may focus on organisms crucial to specific soil functions, such as plant symbionts, pathogens, decomposers, bioremediators, and invasive species (Griffiths *et al.*, 2016; Muñoz-Rojas, 2018; Stone *et al.*, 2016).

However, biodiversity estimates can be influenced by the choice of methodology, as indicated by prior studies (Blackman *et al.*, 2024; Bruce *et al.*, 2021; Jurburg *et al.*, 2021). Sampling design (Dickie *et al.*, 2018; Porter *et al.*, 2019), DNA-extraction method (e.g. Delmont *et al.*, 2011; Dopheide *et al.*, 2019; Wagner *et al.*, 2015), the quantity of source material used (e.g. Porter *et al.*, 2019; Taberlet *et al.*, 2012b), soil preservation (e.g. Guerrieri *et al.*, 2023), primer choice (e.g. Elbrecht *et al.*, 2019; Giebner *et al.*, 2020; Marquina *et al.*, 2019) and bioinformatic pipeline (e.g. Brandt *et al.*, 2021; Joos *et al.*, 2020) have all been documented as factors that can significantly impact final results. Hence, making well-considered decisions during the design of metabarcoding studies is essential. In context of European policies, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has recently developed protocols for the comprehensive monitoring of soil biodiversity in topsoil samples, which covers both micro- and macroorganisms, adding a biodiversity component to the LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey) Soil Survey (Orgiazzi *et al.*, 2022). For the 2018 LUCAS Soil biodiversity campaign, one DNA-extraction method and four primer sets were chosen to cover the broadest possible spectrum of soil organisms. The four target groups, along with their corresponding target genes, include archaea (16S), bacteria (16S), fungi (ITS) and other eukaryotes (18S). Recent results suggest that cropland soils have higher biodiversity than forests or unmanaged grasslands (Königer *et al.*, 2023; Labouyrie *et al.*, 2023). This finding is unexpected and contrasts with previous observations that reported a decline in biodiversity with increasing land-use intensity (Van Eekeren *et al.*, 2008).

Our primary objective was to conduct a comparative analysis between the LUCAS protocols and newly developed national protocols, using eDNA metabarcoding (**Table 2**). This analysis aimed to examine genetic and taxonomic diversity within the eleven LUCAS Biopoints situated in Belgium. It evaluates whether analysing the 0-10 and 10-30 cm layer separately, increasing soil sample sizes, combining more subsamples, and the amplification of DNA with more specific primer sets affects soil biodiversity detection and diversity estimates. To assess whether there is a difference in the amount of biodiversity

information deeper soils vs surface layers harbour, we analyzed the 0–10 cm and 10–30 cm layers separately, and compared that to the 0–30 cm as in the LUCAS protocol.

Evaluating alternative methodologies might be especially important for soil organisms other than prokaryotes and microbial eukaryotes, as best practices for their monitoring using eDNA are less established (Lara *et al.*, 2022). Incorporating sampling protocols, DNA-extraction methods and primer sets targeting specific functional groups which might have been partially overlooked by the methodology used for the 2018 LUCAS Soil Biodiversity component (e.g. Collembola and Annelida), could contribute towards a more comprehensive understanding of the status of European soil biomes. We hypothesised that for Annelida, Collembola, and Arthropoda (i) in general the universal 18S primers do not provide sufficient taxonomic resolution at the species and genus level, and (ii) might not capture the same richness and diversity patterns as group-specific primers.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Soil sampling and sample pre-processing

As part of EJP SOIL WP6 Task 6.3, we performed double sampling at 11 LUCAS Biopoints in Belgium within the framework of the 2022 LUCAS Soil survey, in October 2022 (**Table 1**). At each Biopoint, topsoil samples were taken according to two sampling schemes and at the same time: the LUCAS sampling protocol (ESTAT, 2022), which includes taking subsamples at 5 locations to a depth of 30 cm (**Fig. 1**), with samples collected twice (once for shipment to JRC and once for retention), and the Cmon sampling protocol (Lettens *et al.*, 2024), which includes taking subsamples at 16 locations, with samples collected in two layers (0-10 cm and 10-30 cm, here referred to as INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 respectively). In the woodland biopoints that had a forest floor, the forest floor was sampled separately. The center points of both sampling schemes coincided but the sampled area of Cmon is 625% larger than the LUCAS plot.

Figure 1. LUCAS sampling scheme consisting of 5 subsamples (left) superimposed on the Flemish Cmon sampling scheme consisting of 16 subsamples in a 10x10 m grid cell. Center points of both schemes coincide (right).

The sampling depth was 0-20 cm during the LUCAS 2018 survey, but increased to 0-30 cm for the LUCAS 2022 survey. This 0-30 cm compares well with the two depth layers (0-10 cm and 10-30 cm) of the topsoil sampled following the Cmon sampling protocol (**Fig. 2**). LUCAS soil sampling is performed using a

Figure 2. Sampling depths of LUCAS and Cmon sampling protocols.

spade excavating a slice of soil of about 3 cm thick until 30 cm of depth. From this slice the central part is collected as a subsample. In Cmon, disturbed soil subsamples are collected with a gouge auger between 0-10 and 10-30 cm depth.

Prior to sampling, all equipment (spade, augers, spatulas, containers) was sterilised using VIRKON (disinfectant), in order to prevent

contamination. For each sampling scheme and depth interval, all collected subsamples were thoroughly mixed in a container to get a composite sample. From this composite sample, a subsample was taken using Falcon tubes (50 mL), which were filled with soil and immediately stored in a mobile freezer (-20°C).

Apart from the Falcon tubes for molecular analysis, 500 g of the remaining composite sample was taken for physico-chemical analysis in the INBO soil laboratory. The following soil characteristics were determined using ISO standard methods: bulk density (ISO 11272), coarse fragment content (ISO 11464), and soil texture by laser diffraction (ISO 13320), with pretreatment following the pipette/sieving method outlined in ISO 11277. Additionally, pH-KCl (ISO 10390), electrical conductivity (ISO 11265), total organic carbon (ISO 10694), carbonate content (measured as total inorganic carbon using a total analyzer), and total nitrogen (ISO 13878) were analyzed. All physicochemical data of the Biopoints and 165 regular LUCAS points is reported in a separate EJP SOIL Double Sampling report for Flanders (De Vos, Bruno, 2025).

LUCAS soil samples from all 11 Biopoints were shipped to JRC for molecular analysis in the central lab in October 2022. However, by the end of the EJP SOIL project (January 2025), the soil biodiversity data for these samples were not yet available for comparison. Anticipating this delay, we used the duplicate LUCAS soil samples which were kept frozen at the INBO genetic laboratory instead. Unfortunately, we did not have sufficient LUCAS sampling material from the Biopoints in Deurne and Herentals to include them in the comparison study. The nine Biopoints with enough material for molecular analysis that were used in this comparison are indicated in bold in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of the Belgian Biopoints sampled for comparison with LUCAS 2022 central lab data. The Biopoints for which the sampling schemes are compared are indicated in bold.

Location	LUCAS-ID	Region	Land-use	Sampling date	Latitude	Longitude
Bredene	38363148	Flanders	Cropland	19/10/2022	51.2350	3.0437
Marke	38443098	Flanders	Woodland	19/10/2022	50.7946	3.2238
Deurne*	39343134	Flanders	Grassland	27/10/2022	51.1848	4.4590
Herentals*	39623132	Flanders	Grassland	27/10/2022	51.1854	4.8607
Diepenbeek	40003102	Flanders	Woodland	20/10/2022	50.9395	5.4300
Molenbeek	39783064	Brussels	Park	10/10/2022	50.8528	4.2991
Burdinne	39203098	Wallonia	Cropland	20/10/2022	50.5856	5.1530
Seneffe	39123062	Wallonia	Grassland	18/10/2022	50.5240	4.2265
Cerfontaine	39203022	Wallonia	Grassland	17/10/2022	50.1719	4.3811
Genappe	39303074	Wallonia	Cropland	18/10/2022	50.6447	4.4663
Sombrefe	39383058	Wallonia	Cropland	17/10/2022	50.5067	4.5957

Figure 3. *Impression of Belgian Biopoints at the time of sampling.*

This study was conducted on the 9 Belgian Biopoints of which four were cropland, two were grassland, one was a Park in Molenbeek, Brussels, and two were woodland (**Fig. 3**). Despite the uneven distribution of land-use categories and the limited number of Biopoints, the LUCAS study remains a valuable framework for assessing the effects of sampling schemes and depths.

2.2. Molecular analysis protocol

High-quality mitochondrial 16S and eukaryotic 18S rRNA gene libraries were successfully constructed for a total of 35 soil samples (**Table S1**). DNA-extraction was performed using two distinct methods: (i) **without pre-treatment with phosphate buffer**, following the LUCAS soil biodiversity protocol (prior to PCR-amplification with the 18S primers (18SnoP)): each soil sample was thoroughly homogenised, and between 0.170 g and 0.480 g was used in triplicate for DNA-extraction with the DNeasy Powersoil Pro kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's instructions; and (ii) **with pre-treatment with phosphate buffer to focus on extracellular DNA** (Taberlet *et al.*, 2012b; prior to PCR-amplification with the Annelida-specific primers (Olig01), Collembola-specific primers (Coll01), Arthropoda-specific primers (Inse01), and 18S primers (18SP)): 27 ml of freshly prepared phosphate buffer (Na_2HPO_4 ; 0.12 M; pH \approx 8) was added to the 20 g soil sample. After homogenising the buffer/soil mixture for 30 min on an overhead rotator, a 1 ml aliquot of the supernatant was recovered in triplicate, centrifuged for 10 min at 10 000 rcf, and 500 μl of the resulting supernatant was used in the DNA-extraction with the DNeasy Powersoil Pro kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's instructions but skipping the lysis step. After DNA-extraction, an equal volume of each replicate was pooled per soil sample.

Table 2. A comparative overview of the LUCAS and INBO sampling and molecular analysis protocol.

LUCAS PROTOCOL	INBO PROTOCOL
Sampling design	
Composite of 5 subsamples, 0 - 30 cm layer	Composite of 16 subsamples, 0 - 10 cm and 10 - 30 cm layer analysed separately Forest floor sample (LFH layers)
DNA-extraction	
3 x 0.2 \pm 10% g of soil using Qiagen DNeasy PowerSoil HTP 96 Kit Q12955-4	3 x 0.25 \pm 10% g of soil using Qiagen DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Fungi, Bacteria, Archaea, Protista)
	3 x 20 \pm 10% g of soil using Qiagen DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit, with pre-treatment with phosphate buffer and without lysis step (Annelida, Collembola, Arthropoda)
Primers	
Archaea 16S: SSU1ArF (TCCGGTTGATCCYGCBRG) + SSU1000ArR (GGCCATGCAMYWCCTCTC)	Archaea 16S: SSU1ArF (TCCGGTTGATCCYGCBRG) + SSU1000ArR (GGCCATGCAMYWCCTCTC)

Eukaryote ITS region: ITS9mun (GTACACACCGCCCGTCG) + ITS4ngsUni (CGCCTSCSCTTANTDATATGC).	Eukaryote ITS region: ITS9mun (GTACACACCGCCCGTCG) + ITS4ngsUni (CGCCTSCSCTTANTDATATGC).
Eukaryote SSU (18S) region: Euk575F (ASCYGYGGTAAAYWCCAGC) + Euk895R (TCHNHGNATTTACCNCT)	Eukaryote SSU (18S) region: Euk575F (ASCYGYGGTAAAYWCCAGC) + Euk895R (TCHNHGNATTTACCNCT)
/	Annelida 16S: Olig01F (CAAGAAGACCCTATAGAGCTT) + Olig01R (CCTGTTATCCCTAAGGTARCT)
/	Collembola 16S: Coll01F (ACGCTGTTATCCCTWAGG) + Coll01R (GACGATAAGACCCTWTAGA)
/	Arthropoda 16S: Inse01F (RGACGAGAAGACCCTATARA) + Inse01R (ACGCTGTTATCCCTAARGTA)

For **Annelida** (Olig01), PCRs targeting the mitochondrial 16S rRNA gene were performed using the forward primer Olig01F (5'-CAAGAAGACCCTATAGAGCTT-3') and reverse primer Olig01R (5'-CCTGTTATCCCTAAGGTARCT-3') (Bienert *et al.*, 2012). For **Collembola** (Coll01), the 16S mitochondrial rDNA gene was amplified using the forward Coll01F (5'-ACGCTGTTATCCCTWAGG-3') and the reverse Coll01R (5'-GACGATAAGACCCTWTAGA-3') primers (Janssen, 2018). For **Arthropoda** (Inse01), the 16S mitochondrial rDNA gene was amplified using the forward Inse01F (5'-RGACGAGAAGACCCTATARA-3') and reverse Inse01R (5'-ACGCTGTTATCCCTAARGTA-3') primers (Guerrieri *et al.*, 2023; Taberlet *et al.*, 2018). For **Eukaryota** (18S), PCRs targeting the hypervariable V4 region of the 18S rRNA gene were carried out using the forward Euk575F (5'-ASCYGYGGTAAAYWCCAGC-3') and the reverse Euk895R (5'-TCHNHGNATTTACCNCT-3') primers (Guerra *et al.*, 2021).

For **Olig01**, **Coll01**, **Inse01** and **18S** primers, PCR was carried out in a 25- μ l reaction volume containing 3 μ l of template DNA (1-20 ng μ l⁻¹), 2.5 μ l 10X PCR Buffer II (100 mM TrisHCl, 500 mM KCl; ThermoFisher Scientific), 1 μ l dNTP mix (10 mM; ThermoFischer Scientific), 2 μ l primer mix (2.5 μ M each of indexed forward and reverse primer; except for the 18S primer mix which uses a composition of 2.5 μ M indexed forward and 10 μ M indexed reverse primer to prevent amplification biases), 0.5 μ l ultrapure

non-acetylated bovine serum albumin (10 mg ml⁻¹; ThermoFisher Scientific), 2.5 MgCl₂ (25 mM; ThermoFisher Scientific), 0.25 µl AmpliTaq Gold DNA Polymerase (5 U µl⁻¹; ThermoFisher Scientific) and 13.25 µl DEPC-treated water (ThermoFisher Scientific). For **Olig01**, **Coll01**, and **Inse01** primers, PCR began with an initial denaturation step of 10 minutes at 95 °C, followed by 55 cycles of denaturation (30 seconds at 95 °C), annealing (30 seconds at 51.5 °C for Coll01 and Inse01, or 55 °C for Olig01), and elongation (1 minute at 72 °C). For **18S** primers, an initial denaturation step of 12 min at 95 °C was followed by 35 cycles of 20 s denaturation at 95 °C, 30 s annealing at 55 °C and an elongation step at 72 °C for 1 min. After a final elongation of 7 min at 72 °C, PCR products were visualised on 2% agarose gel and concentration was measured fluorometrically using the Quantus kit (Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. If amplification was successful, PCR triplicates for each sample were pooled to minimise potential biases. The pooled PCR products from Olig01, Coll01, and 18S (from both extraction methods) were purified using Agencourt AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter Inc.), while the Inse01 PCR products were purified using BluePippin (Sage Science), following the manufacturer's instructions. Inline index sequences were incorporated into each primer during design, resulting in a unique dual-matched indexing system for each PCR. This approach minimizes sample misassignment during read demultiplexing. Additionally, variable-length indices were used to enhance the likelihood that neighboring clusters on the Illumina flow cell sequence the internal PCR-amplified target fragment out-of-phase (See Brys *et al.*, 2021 for further details).

Amplicon libraries were sequenced on the Illumina MiSeq platform for Coll01 and Olig01 (2 × 150 bp, paired-end, v3 chemistry), and on the Illumina NovaSeq platform for Inse01 (2 × 150 bp, paired-end) and 18S (2 × 250 bp, paired-end). Each run with either mitochondrial 16S or 18S samples contained one mock community, containing two fungal and eight bacterial species (i.e., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) at known concentrations (ZymoBIOMICS Microbial Community DNA Standard II, Zymo Research; diluted 1:10), one negative PCR control and one negative DNA-extraction to check overall run quality and benchmark processing variables, as well as two PCR replicate samples.

For **Fungi**, PCRs targeting the ITS region (including the 18S V9 subregion) were performed using the forward ITS9mun (5'-GTACACACCGCCCGTCG-3') and reverse ITS4ngsUni

(5'-CGCCTSCSCTTANTDATATGC-3') primers (Tedersoo & Anslan, 2019). For **Archaea**, the V1-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using the forward SSU1ArF (5'-TCCGGTTGATCCYGCBRG-3') and the reverse SSU1000ArR (5'-GGCCATGCAMYWCCTCTC-3') primers (Bahram *et al.*, 2019).

For **Fungi** and **Archaea** primers, PCR was carried out in a 25- μ l reaction volume containing 6 μ l of the template DNA (1-20 ng μ l⁻¹), 2.5 μ l 10X PCR Buffer II (100 mM TrisHCl, 500 mM KCl; ThermoFisher Scientific), 1 μ l dNTP mix (10 mM; ThermoFischer Scientific), 2 μ l primer mix (2.5 μ M each of indexed forward and reverse primer), 0.5 μ l ultrapure non-acetylated bovine serum albumin (10 mg ml⁻¹; ThermoFisher Scientific), 2.5 MgCl₂ (25 mM; ThermoFisher Scientific), 0.25 μ l AmpliTaq Gold DNA Polymerase (5 U μ l⁻¹; ThermoFisher Scientific) and 10.25 μ l DEPC-treated water (ThermoFisher Scientific).

The PCR started with an initial denaturation step of 10 min at 95 °C and was followed by 35 or 40 cycles, for Archaea or Fungi primers respectively, of 30 s denaturation at 95 °C 30 s annealing at 55 °C, and an elongation step at 72 °C for 1 min. After a final elongation of 7 min at 72 °C, PCR products were visualised on 1% agarose gel and concentration was measured fluorometrically using the Quantus kit (Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. If amplification was successful, PCR triplicates for each sample were equimolarly pooled to minimise potential biases. The pooled PCR products were subsequently purified with Agencourt AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter Inc.) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.3. Bioinformatics

2.3.1. Soil fauna and protists

Prior to any additional processing, we evaluated the quality of the raw reads using FastQC software V0.11.7 (Andrews, 2010). Next, an identical approach was followed for demultiplexing the FASTQ files containing the Olig01, Coll01, Inse01 and 18S sequences. A custom demultiplexing script (https://gitlab.com/ahaegeman/eDNA_INBO-ILVO/-/blob/master/eDNA_demultiplexing.sh) previously designed by Brys *et al.* (2021) was used to efficiently demultiplex dual-indexed libraries. This script uses sabre version 1.000 (<https://github.com/najoshi/sabre>), as this software is capable of handling inline barcodes of varying lengths. This custom demultiplexing script employs multiple calls to sabre to allocate read pairs to respective samples. This process is executed separately for both forward and reverse reads

and in both forward and reverse directions. A read pair is assigned to a specific sample only if both its forward and reverse barcodes match without any errors.

Following the demultiplexing step, a parallel pipeline was executed for **Olig01**, **Coll01**, and **Inse01**. Forward and reverse reads were merged using PEAR version 0.9.11 (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). This merging process adhered to the following parameters: a minimum overlap of 10 nucleotides; a minimum and maximum possible length of the assembled sequences of 93 and 255 nucleotides respectively for the Olig01 dataset, of 76 and 243 nucleotides respectively for the Coll01 dataset, and of 93 and 290 nucleotides respectively for the Inse01 dataset; and a maximum proportion of uncalled bases in a read of 1 nucleotide.

Next, the reads from the Olig01, Coll01, and Inse01 datasets were subjected to quality filtering using USEARCH version 11.0.667 (Edgar, 2010) with the following criteria: a maximum expected error of 1 and a minimum length requirement of 93 nucleotides. All filtered reads were dereplicated and sorted by size using VSEARCH version 2.22.1 (Rognes *et al.*, 2016). Reads were first denoised and again sorted by size before OTUs were identified using an identity threshold of 92% for Olig01, 85% for Coll01, and 96% for Inse01. These thresholds were selected for each taxon on the basis of the distributions of pairwise sequence similarities within and between species of the same genus for each marker (Bonin *et al.*, 2022). The selected thresholds allow to minimise the risk that multiple individuals belonging to the same species are assigned to different molecular operational taxonomic units (OTUs), while limiting the probability that distinct species are collapsed in one single OTU (Bonin *et al.*, 2022). Differences in thresholds are related to differences in taxonomic resolution across markers (Guerrieri *et al.*, 2021).

For taxonomic assignment of the Olig01, Coll01, and Inse01 datasets, we built sequence reference databases for each primer set using two different approaches: the CRABS software (Jeunen *et al.*, 2023) and the OBITools software suite. Using CRABS, reference sequences from the NCBI (accessed on 11/08/2023) and EMBL (version 143; 11/08/2023) repositories were retrieved through an *in silico* PCR, allowing four mismatches per primer. This step included an optional pairwise global alignment (pga) step to capture sequences with missing primer-binding regions. Taxonomic lineage assignment was performed using NCBI's taxonomy, and sequences were dereplicated to retain all unique sequences per species. The databases were further curated using the 'seq_cleanup' module, retaining only sequences

within the appropriate length range, with no more than two ambiguous bases, and with a specified species name. Using OBITools, we built reference databases from EMBL (version 143; 11/08/2023) by running the *ecopcr* program (Ficetola *et al.*, 2010) to perform an *in silico* PCR with the primer pairs used in the experiment, allowing three mismatches per primer. The obtained reference sequences were curated by retaining only those assigned at the species, genus, and family levels. The taxonomic assignment was performed using both LotuS2 (Özkurt *et al.*, 2022) in '-taxOnly' modus and 'obi ecotag' from OBITools to check for consistency and increase the likelihood that taxonomic assignments are as correct as possible (given the currently available public reference data). Both methods used the newly created custom reference databases. For both methods, only OTUs with a best identity above predefined cutoffs were considered. For Olig01, the thresholds were $\geq 60\%$ at phylum level, $\geq 65\%$ at class level, $\geq 70\%$ at order level, $\geq 75\%$ at family level, $\geq 80\%$ at genus level, and $\geq 94\%$ at species level. For Coll01, the cutoffs were $\geq 60\%$ at phylum level, $\geq 70\%$ at order level, $\geq 74\%$ at family level, $\geq 79\%$ at genus level, and $\geq 85\%$ at species level. For Inse01, the thresholds were $\geq 60\%$ at phylum level, $\geq 70\%$ at class level, $\geq 74\%$ at order level, $\geq 84\%$ at family level, $\geq 86\%$ at genus level, and $\geq 96\%$ at species level.

For both **18S** datasets, demultiplexed reads were first processed separately using the DADA2 package version 3.10 (Callahan *et al.*, 2016) within R version 4.0 (R Core Team, 2021). The first step involved primer removal from the raw reads by trimming the initial 18 nucleotides from both the forward and reverse reads using the 'trimLeft' command. Based on a manual inspection of FastQC files, the forward and reverse reads were truncated at base pairs 237 and 241 for the 18SP dataset, and at 240 for the 18SnoP dataset, using the 'truncLen' command. Filtering was performed with a maximum 'expected errors' threshold ('maxEE') of 2 for both forward and reverse reads. Reads not matching these criteria were discarded. Following sequence dereplication, sequence variants for the forward and reverse reads were inferred using an error matrix constructed from the first 1e8 bp of the sequences. Singletons were discarded, and paired-end reads were merged with no allowance for mismatches and a required minimum overlap of 20 bp. Sequence tables were constructed using the 'makeSequenceTable' command. Finally, chimeric sequences were removed using the 'removeBimeraDenovo' commands. To compare taxonomic resolution between the PR2 and SILVA reference databases in 18S rRNA gene metabarcoding, we conducted parallel taxonomic assignments using both databases. Taxonomic classification of all ASVs was performed using 'classify.seqs' in Mothur version 1.48.0 (Schloss *et al.*,

2009) with both the PR2 database version 5.0.0 (Guillou *et al.*, 2012) and SILVA database version 138.1. Taxonomic resolution was assessed by comparing the number of unique genus identifications between the two databases. To ensure comparability, we extracted and analyzed sequences specifically assigned to Annelida and Collembola from both classification outputs. For all other analyses presented here, however, we used the output of the taxonomic identifications generated with the PR2 database.

In the context of eDNA metabarcoding, it is well-known that a substantial portion of the sequences detected at low frequencies can be attributed to various sources of noise, including PCR artefacts, contaminants, and sequencing errors. These artefacts have the potential to introduce bias into ecological analyses (Zinger *et al.*, 2019). To mitigate this issue and ensure the reliability of ecological findings, we filtered the data in R version 4.0 (R Core Team, 2021) using phyloseq version 1.16.2 (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013). Specifically, we removed OTUs/ASVs that were observed fewer than two times across all samples (true singletons), and OTUs/ASVs that were found in the NTC (No Template Control) or mock samples. Additionally, after occurrence inspection, mock communities, NTC and replicate samples were removed from the ASV/OTU tables and only one sample with the highest read number was kept among replicates of the same sample. OTUs from the same species were merged using the 'tax_glom' command.

We then generated subsets for Coll01 and Olig01, each containing only OTUs/ASVs from respective taxonomic groups Collembola and Annelida. Additionally, two subsets were created for the Inse01 data: one containing only arthropod species; and one limited to species from the following classes: Insecta, Arachnida, Chilopoda, Diplura, and Malacostraca. Corresponding subsets were also created for the 18S data, including for the three main soil invertebrate groups focused on here (Annelida, Collembola, Arthropoda), as well as additional subsets for Nematoda, Platyhelminthes, Rotifera, Tardigrada and Protista.

To correct for uneven sequencing depth per sample, datasets were rarefied using a random subsampling method to 27,913, 31,655, 1,856, 19,728, and 19,632 reads for Annelida (Olig01), Collembola (Coll01), Fungi (ITS9mun/ITS4ngsUni), protists (18S), and Archaea (SSU1ArF/SSU1000ArR) respectively. For datasets that are subsets of the total data recovered by a primer set designed to target multiple phyla (i.e., 18S, Inse01), non-rarefied data were more often used to avoid unnecessary data loss. Depending on

the analysis, we performed analyses using both rarefied and non-rarefied data to assess the consistency of the results.

2.3.2. Fungi and Archaea

Prior to downstream processing, we assessed the quality of raw sequencing reads using FastQC v0.11.7 (Andrews, 2010). To ensure compatibility with bioinformatics tools and prevent issues arising from abnormal quality scores, we reformatted the quality scores using BBTools (Bushnell, 2022) 'reformat.sh', constraining the Phred quality score range to 2–41. This is useful for preventing abnormal quality scores such as in these error-corrected PacBio reads. Demultiplexing was performed by assigning sequences to samples based on their barcode sequences, allowing a single mismatch per barcode. The Fungi amplicon data was then processed using the NextITS pipeline (Mikryukov *et al.*, 2023) with default parameter settings, implemented within PipeCraft v1.0.0 (Anslan *et al.*, 2017). Taxonomic assignments were carried out using blast searches against the Unite 8 database (Abarenkov *et al.*, 2024), followed by the LCA v0.24 algorithm within LotuS2 (Özkurt *et al.*, 2022), using recommended parameters.

2.4. Statistical analyses

Taxonomic composition and species detection, species richness and diversity (Shannon diversity index), and community composition were analysed and compared across (molecular analysis and sampling) protocols and locations using R version 4.2.0 (R Core Team, 2021), with data manipulation conducted using the dplyr package (Wickham *et al.*, 2024) and visualizations created using ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016).

Taxonomic composition and detection were evaluated by comparing the detection of known taxa across **molecular analysis protocols**, focusing on the differences between group-specific primers (Collembola-specific primers (Coll01), Annelida-specific primers (Olig01), Arthropoda-specific primers (Inse01)) and the universal eukaryotic 18S primers tested here, as well as between different DNA-extraction methods (Powersoil Pro and phosphate buffer extractions). Taxonomic trees were generated using the *metabaR* package in R (version 1.0.0; R Core Team, 2021), displaying the proportion

of reads and OTUs assigned to each taxonomic group and molecular analysis protocol, each time across the complete dataset.

Similarly, the detection of OTUs identified at species level was compared across **sampling protocols** per location (9 locations) only for the group-specific primers (Coll01, Olig01, Inse01, Fungi), through three distinct sets of comparisons: (1) INBO_0_10 versus LUCAS, (2) INBO_10_30 versus LUCAS, and (3) combined INBO protocols versus LUCAS. For the combined INBO comparison, we considered species detected in either INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30 samples. A species was considered unique to a sampling protocol if it was detected only by that protocol at a given sampling location. For each taxonomic group (Annelida, Collembola, and Arthropoda) and each comparison, we calculated the mean number of unique species per location and the total number of unique species across all locations for each protocol. Due to the non-normal distribution of the count data and the paired nature of the sampling design, we used the Wilcoxon signed-rank test to evaluate statistical differences between protocols for all comparisons. To evaluate overall differences among all three protocols simultaneously (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, and LUCAS), we implemented a Friedman test, as a non-parametric alternative to a one-way repeated measures ANOVA. P-values from pairwise comparisons were adjusted using the Bonferroni correction to account for multiple testing. Statistical significance was assessed at $\alpha = 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed in R (R Core Team, 2021). Additionally, the relative abundances of all OTUs and the OTUs that were identified at species level were compared across sampling protocols at each sampling location.

Variation in **diversity** measures was assessed using observed species richness and Shannon diversity indices, with comparisons made across different molecular analysis and sampling protocols. To assess differences in observed species richness and common biodiversity indices among the three sampling protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, and LUCAS), we first evaluated data normality using Shapiro-Wilk tests for each protocol separately. Given the paired nature of our sampling design, with all three protocols applied at each sampling location, we employed a non-parametric Friedman test to account for the blocked structure of the data. The number of complete sampling locations (sites with data for all three protocols) varied by taxonomic group: Annelida ($n = 8$), Collembola ($n = 7$), and Arthropoda ($n = 8$). Following the global test, we conducted post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni corrections to control for multiple comparisons ($\alpha = 0.05$). Additionally, we

calculated effect sizes (Cohen's d) for each pairwise comparison to quantify the magnitude of differences between protocols, with effect sizes interpreted as small ($d = 0.2$), moderate ($d = 0.5$), or large ($d = 0.8$) based on conventional thresholds. Finally, we examined how protocol choice affected the relative ranking of locations. Rank shifts were assessed by comparing the position of each location across protocols, identifying inconsistencies in diversity estimates.

Community composition of samples was compared using Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) based on Bray-Curtis distances to visualize clustering patterns across molecular analyses and sampling protocols.

3. Results

In general, given the limited sample sizes used in this study, the statistical power to detect significant differences between protocols was severely constrained. Consequently, p-values should be interpreted with considerable caution, and emphasis should be placed on observed effect sizes and patterns rather than statistical significance alone. These limitations necessitate that our findings be considered preliminary, serving primarily to identify patterns worthy of investigation in future studies with larger sample sizes.

3.1. Cross-taxa synthesis: soil biodiversity insights

3.1.1. General

A total of 139 OTUs were identified with the **Annelida**-specific primers (Olig01), and classified as Enchytraeidae (111 OTUs), Lumbricidae (21 OTUs), and Naididae (one OTU). Of these, 127 were identified at the genus level (91.37%) and 49 at the species level (35.25%). The top five most abundant Lumbricidae species accounted for a cumulative total of 83.41% of all Lumbricidae sequence reads: *Allolobophora chlorotica* (23.39%), *Lumbricus terrestris* (16.37%), *Aporrectodea longa* (16.20%), *Aporrectodea nocturna* (14.89%), and *Aporrectodea rosea* (12.56%).

The **Collembola**-specific primers (Coll01) identified 148 Collembola OTUs, which were classified as Entomobryomorpha (54 OTUs), Poduromorpha (23 OTUs), Neelipleona (16 OTUs) and Symphypleona (nine OTUs). Of these, 80 were identified at the genus level, and 28 at the species level. *Megalothorax* was the most abundant genus, representing 16.71% of the total reads.

Coleoptera and mites (Mesostigmata and Acari) were the most diverse and abundant soil-dwelling orders detected with the **Arthropoda**-specific primers (Inse01). The Curculionidae family (weevils) showed the highest genetic diversity in our dataset, followed by Elateridae (click beetles), Macrochelidae (predatory mites), Discourellidae (soft-winged flower beetles), Ixodidae (hard ticks), and Pemphigidae (woolly aphids). *Amphimallon solstitiale* (European chafer) was the most abundant species, comprising 20% of Arthropoda reads. 85% of OTUs could be identified at the family level, 46% at genus level, and 31% at species level.

Parallel analyses of soil Fungi, protists, and Archaea were conducted or are still ongoing. The results for Fungi are included separately at the end of the results section of this report, while the analyses of Archaea and protists are still in progress and will be published in v2 of the report. These studies will

provide insights into the effects of different sampling protocols on these microbial taxa and serve to complement our current findings. This section integrates findings on soil fauna biodiversity, focusing on Annelida, Collembola, and Arthropoda.

3.1.2. Effects of different protocols on taxa detection and diversity

3.1.2.1. Molecular analysis protocol

Taxa detection - The Collembola-specific primers (Coll01) detected 21 genera, including the most abundant genus (based on Coll01) *Megalothorax*, which were missed by the universal 18S primers. Similarly, Annelida-specific primers (Olig01) detected 12 genera and 46 species, including the dominant genus *Aporrectodea* (based on Olig01), which 18S failed to detect. In both taxa, the universal 18S primers missed the majority of genera detected by the group-specific primers. In contrast, the insect-specific primers (Inse01) and universal eukaryotic primers (18S) showed complementary detection patterns, with only six orders and 16 families shared between them. Inse01 uniquely identified six orders and 25 families, including abundant genera such as *Amphimallon* and *Athous*, while 18S uniquely detected six orders and 31 families, recovering a broader diversity of mites. Inse01 was more effective for flying insects, as well as a broader range of beetles.

Comparisons of DNA-extraction methods using the 18S primers revealed that the phosphate buffer method (18SP) outperformed the Powersoil Pro method (18SnoP). The phosphate buffer method detected six additional Collembola genera and seven species, two additional Annelida genera (including the dominant *Fridericia*), and 22 insect genera and 18 species that were missed by Powersoil Pro. In contrast, the Powersoil Pro method detected only one additional genus and two species across all three groups.

When evaluating the variability in estimated community composition across identical samples and comparing results derived from both group-specific and universal Eukaryotic primers, we found that, in general, samples from the same location or land-use category, taken with different sampling protocols, tend to have a more similar community composition when using the group-specific primers than when using the universal eukaryotic 18S primers. This suggests that the group-specific primers better capture community composition patterns, as it reflects the expectation that samples from the same location or land-use category share more similar species compositions than those from different locations or

land-use categories.

After performing parallel taxonomic assignments of 18S ASVs using both the SILVA and PR2 reference databases, our study revealed consistently higher taxonomic resolution with the PR2 database for both Annelida and Collembola. The PR2 database resolved 11 unique genera for Annelida and 16 for Collembola, whereas the SILVA database did not provide genus-level resolution, only assigning ASVs to higher taxonomic levels (mostly phylum and class).

Species richness - The comparison of observed species richness between the group-specific primers and the universal 18S primers (18SP and 18SnoP) was conducted based solely on rank, as a direct comparison is not possible between different primers. For the Collembola and Arthropoda, samples ranked mostly similarly based on species richness across molecular analysis methods, with some exceptions where ranks were either higher or lower for specific samples. In contrast, for the Annelida, there was a more significant difference in ranks across multiple samples.

3.1.2.2. Sampling protocol

3.1.2.2.1. The effect of sampling protocol on species detection

Unique detection of known species per sampling protocol. Across all three groups (Annelida, Collembola and Arthropoda), the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol consistently detected the highest number of unique species, followed by the LUCAS sampling protocol, while the INBO_10_30 protocol detected the fewest unique species. However, the statistical significance of these differences varied among groups and sampling protocols comparisons. **The differences were most pronounced in Annelida** ($p = 0.007$), where INBO_0_10 significantly outperformed INBO_10_30 ($p = 0.02$), LUCAS significantly outperformed INBO_10_30 ($p = 0.03$) and INBO_0_10 outperformed LUCAS ($p = 0.055$). For Collembola, while none of the comparisons reached statistical significance, the effect size calculations suggest that the INBO_0_10 protocol may be more effective at detecting species compared to both LUCAS and INBO_10_30 protocols. Based on the calculated effect sizes, the arthropod communities showed substantial differences between surface samples (INBO_0_10) and LUCAS ($d = 1.43$; $p[\text{adj}] = 0.062$), moderate differences between the INBO soil layers ($d = 0.69$), and negligible differences between deeper INBO_10_30 samples and LUCAS ($d = -0.07$). When combining both INBO protocols, the INBO sampling protocol consistently detected more unique species than LUCAS across all taxonomic groups (Annelida p

= 0.01; Arthropoda $p = 0.04$; Collembola $p = 0.07$). Overall, prevalence estimates based on INBO_10_30 and LUCAS were generally lower than those based on INBO_0_10. Many species were detected exclusively by INBO_0_10 and/or LUCAS, while very few were exclusively detected using INBO_10_30, suggesting that **the deeper 10-30 cm soil layer provides little additional value for quantifying important soil invertebrate (Annelida, Collembola, Arthropoda) diversity based on eDNA.**

3.1.2.2.2. The effect of sampling protocol on species richness and diversity

Statistical tests revealed a significantly **higher species richness captured by the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol compared to the LUCAS protocol** for Collembola and Arthropoda, but not for Annelida. For Annelida, differences in richness and diversity across the three sampling protocols were not statistically significant, but the effect size for richness was moderate for INBO_0_10 vs LUCAS ($d = 0.66$), and the highest observed across all sampling protocol comparisons. The most pronounced average species richness rank changes of sampled locations across taxonomic groups were observed between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 protocols, with Collembola showing the highest change, followed by Arthropoda and Annelida. This suggests that vertical stratification (0-10 cm vs. 10-30 cm) has the strongest effect on species richness rankings of sampled locations, particularly for smaller soil organisms like Collembola. For Shannon diversity, the largest rank changes were observed in Arthropoda, particularly between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS, and INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30. This indicates that both sampling depth and protocol type substantially affect the diversity patterns of arthropods. Effect sizes ranged from small to moderate, with the largest effect observed for Annelida between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 protocols ($d = 0.55$). Overall, the analyses suggest that depth has a more profound effect than sampling intensity on the soil faunal diversity captured, and that the combination of surface sampling and higher subsample number recovers the highest diversity of all three sampling protocols tested.

With the exception of cropland samples, species richness and Shannon diversity were highest in samples collected using the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol in all **land-use types** across all groups (Annelida, Collembola and Arthropoda), with **the most pronounced differences between sampling protocols observed in grasslands** and recreational areas for Annelida, **in forests** for Collembola species richness, and in grasslands for Collembola Shannon diversity. For Arthropoda, the biggest differences in both

richness and diversity were found in forests. Notably, one of the forest plots (Diepenbeek) also shows the most dramatic shift across different sampling protocols for Collembola, Arthropoda, and Fungi, considering both observed species richness and Shannon diversity. Under the INBO_0_10 protocol, it ranks among the highest, whereas with the INBO_10_30 and/or LUCAS protocols, it falls among the lowest.

For Collembola and Arthropoda, **richness and diversity generally increased towards less intensely managed ecosystems**, when using the INBO_0_10 and, to a lesser extent, the LUCAS sampling protocols, with the highest values recorded in forests. In contrast, **the INBO_10_30 sampling protocol failed to capture such a pattern**, and richness was similar across all land-use types, while Shannon diversity even decreased towards the less intensely managed ecosystems.

3.1.2.2.3. Forest floor vs mineral soil

In Diepenbeek, across the three groups (collembolans, arthropods and annelids), the forest floor sampling protocol consistently recovered the highest unique genetic diversity (OTUs). Arthropods showed the most distinct result, with 50% of taxa detected only in the forest floor, compared to 11% for collembolans and 29% for annelids. When combining detections from the forest floor and INBO_0_10 protocols, 42% of all Collembola taxa, 70% of arthropod taxa and 37% of annelid taxa were only detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols. These results indicate **substantially different genetic diversity can be recovered in both the forest floor and mineral soil**. Of the three functional groups, the forest floor appears the most crucial for recovering non-Collembola arthropod diversity.

In Gontrode, across the three groups (collembolans, arthropods and annelids), the forest floor sampling protocol consistently recovered the highest unique genetic diversity. Arthropods again showed the most distinct result, with 44% of taxa detected only in the forest floor, compared to 29% for collembolans and 17% for annelids. When combining detections from the forest floor and INBO_0_10 protocols, 69% of all Collembola taxa, 81% of arthropod taxa and 72% of annelid taxa were only detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols. Notably, arthropods showed minimal overlap (3%) across sampling protocols (versus 24 and 22% for collembolans and annelids respectively). The INBO_10_30 protocol contributed minimal unique diversity across all groups, with only two unique arthropod OTUs

and no unique annelid or non-Collembola arthropod OTUs detected by this sampling protocol alone.

3.1.2.2.4. Summary forest floor vs mineral soil

Sampling **the forest floor uncovered a significant proportion of biodiversity not detected by any mineral soil sampling protocol**. Depending on the location and taxonomic group, up to 50% of taxa was uniquely detected in the forest floor. Of all groups surveyed, the forest floor seems the most important for detecting non-Collembola arthropod diversity. In the two forest locations analyzed here, the INBO_10_30 sampling protocol contributes minimal unique genetic diversity, and **the combination of forest floor and 0-10 cm sampling captures as good as all diversity** recovered for all taxonomic groups (Annelida, Collembola and Arthropoda).

3.2. Annelida

3.2.1. Summary

A total of 139 OTUs were identified and classified as Enchytraeidae (111 OTUs), Lumbricidae (21 OTUs) and Naididae (one OTU). Of these, 127 were identified at genus level (91.37%) and 49 at species level (35.25%). The top five most abundant Lumbricidae species accounted for a cumulative total of 83.41% of all Lumbricidae sequence reads: *Allolobophora chlorotica* (23.39%), *Lumbricus terrestris* (16.37%), *Aporrectodea longa* (16.20%), *Aporrectodea nocturna* (14.89%) and *Aporrectodea rosea* (12.56%).

In the comparison between **molecular analysis protocols**, the Annelida-specific primers (Olig01) identified **12 genera** and 46 species **that were not identified when using the universal 18S primers**. Notably, this included the second most abundant genus (based on Olig01), *Aporrectodea*, and four out of the five most abundant species. The relative observed species richness of several samples differed substantially between Olig01 and the universal 18S primers. The two methods for extracting DNA showed similar results in detecting taxa (**Fig. 7**) when using the 18S primers. However, the phosphate buffer method identified two genera and two species that the standard Powersoil Pro method missed, including the most common genus in our study, *Fridericia*. When analyzing community composition, samples taken from the same location and processed with different sampling protocols had a more similar community composition when using the Olig01 primer set than with the universal 18S primers.

When comparing the performance of the Annelida-specific primers across the **three sampling protocols** (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30 and LUCAS), the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol detected the highest number of unique species that were missed by the other sampling protocols, followed by LUCAS in second place, while INBO_10_30 detected the fewest unique species. The differences between protocols were statistically significant. Forest floor sampling recovered the highest unique annelid diversity across all sampled layers, with minimal overlap between forest floor and mineral soil protocols. Estimated species richness was higher with the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol compared to LUCAS and INBO_10_30 in six out of nine locations. Differences in richness and diversity across the three sampling protocols were not statistically significant, but the effect size for richness was moderate for INBO_0_10 vs LUCAS ($d = 0.66$), and the highest observed across all sampling protocol comparisons. With the exception of cropland samples, richness and diversity (Shannon) were lowest in samples taken using the INBO_10_30 protocol.

The biggest difference in richness and diversity between sampling protocols was observed in grasslands and recreation. Both richness and diversity was highest in recreation (Molenbeek), and Shannon diversity was lower in forests compared to croplands and grasslands. The community composition captured using different sampling protocols is more similar for the two forest and one recreation location(s), than for two grassland and two cropland locations. Overall, the analyses suggest that depth has a more profound effect than sampling intensity on the annelid soil biodiversity captured, and that the combination of surface sampling and higher subsample number recovers the highest diversity of all three sampling protocols tested.

3.2.2. General

In total, Illumina sequencing yielded 7,593,382 reads for the Annelida-specific primers (Olig01) which, after quality control and filtering, resulted in a read count varying from 27,913 to 451,191, averaging at 154,337 reads across all 36 samples. A total of 139 OTUs were identified, and classified as Enchytraeidae (111 OTUs), Lumbricidae (21 OTUs), and Naididae (one OTU). Six OTUs remained unclassified at the family level. A total of 108 Enchytraeid and 19 Lumbricid OTUs were classified at the genus level, of which 35 (Enchytraeidae) and 14 (Lumbricidae) could be further identified at the species level (**Table S2, Fig. 4**)

After correcting for uneven sequencing depth per sample, Enchytraeidae and Lumbricidae accounted for 69 and 31% of the total reads, respectively, while Naididae and the OTUs that remained unclassified at the family level accounted for less than 0.3%. *Fridericia*, *Aporrectodea*, and *Enchytraeus* were the most abundant genera overall, accounting for 40, 19, and 11% of the total reads, respectively, while the remaining genera consisted of *Achaeta* (10%), *Allolobophora* (6%), *Lumbricus* (6%), *Marionina* (2%), and *Henlea* (2%). *Buchholzia*, *Chamaedrillus*, *Mesenchytraeus*, *Enchytronia*, *Rhyacodrilus*, *Cernosvitoviella*, *Cognettia* and *Oconnorella* each represented less than 1% of the total read count.

The most abundant species across all samples is *Allolobophora chlorotica*, accounting for 6.3% of total reads, followed by *Fridericia christeri* (6%), *Fridericia OTU620* (4.86%), *Lumbricus terrestris* (4.42%), and *Aporrectodea longa* (4.37%). The most prevalent OTUs/species across all eleven sampled locations were *Fridericia OTU662* and *Fridericia christeri* (present at nine locations), followed by *Allolobophora chlorotica*, *Enchytraeus buchholzi*, and *Enchytraeus OTU394* (eight locations). *Fridericia galba*, *Enchytraeus christenseni*, *Aporrectodea rosea*, *Fridericia heliota* and *Fridericia bulboides* were each

detected at seven of these locations, while *Lumbricus terrestris*, *Aporrectodea longa* and *Aporrectodea caliginosa* were observed at six locations.

When examining the identified **Lumbricidae** species within this study, the top five most abundant species accounted for a cumulative total of 72% of all Lumbricidae sequence reads: *Allolobophora chlorotica* (20%), *Lumbricus terrestris* (14%), *Aporrectodea longa* (14%), *Aporrectodea nocturna* (13%), and *Aporrectodea rosea* (11%); they were followed by *Aporrectodea caliginosa* (6%), *Aporrectodea icterica* (4%) and *Lumbricus rubellus* (4%). When focusing on known **Enchytraeidae** species detected in this study, the top five identified Enchytraeidae species collectively accounted for 29% of the total Enchytraeidae sequence reads: *Fridericia christeri* (9%), *Achaeta bifollicula* (6%), *Fridericia heliota* (6%), *Fridericia galba* (5%), and *Fridericia ratzeli* (3%). *Fridericia isseli*, *Henlea andreae*, *Enchytraeus christenseni*, *Enchytraeus buchholzi*, *Fridericia connata*, *Fridericia sylvatica*, *Enchytraeus bulbosus*, *Marionina clavata*, *Marionina filiformis* and *Buchholzia fallax* each accounted for 1 to 5% of total Enchytraeid reads, while the other known Enchytraeidae species each accounted for less than 1% of the total Enchytraeidae sequence reads.

Figure 4. Krona plot visualizing all Annelida taxa (based on Olig01). Each ring in the plot represents a hierarchical level (Class - Order - Family - Genus - Species/OTU). The size of the segments reflects the relative read abundance of each taxon across the complete dataset.

3.2.3. Effects of different protocols on taxa detection and diversity

3.2.3.1. Molecular analysis protocol

3.2.3.1.1. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on species and genera detection

The Annelida-specific primers (Olig01) identified **12 genera** and 46 species **which were not identified when using the universal eukaryotic 18S primers** (with the phosphate buffer method used for DNA-extraction; **Table S3, Fig. 5 and 6**). Notably, this included the second most abundant genus (based on the Olig01 dataset), *Aporrectodea*, and four out of the five most abundant species: *Allolobophora chlorotica*, *Fridericia christeri*, *Lumbricus terrestris*, and *Aporrectodea longa*. Four other highly prevalent species were also not detected with the 18S primers (*Aporrectodea rosea*, *Enchytraeus christensen*, *Fridericia galba*, and *Fridericia heliota*). Two genera were reported with the 18S primers which were not detected with the Olig01 primers: *Aeolosoma* and *Hormogaster*.

Figure 5. Annelida taxa detected using universal eukaryotic 18S primers (using the phosphate buffer extraction).

Figure 6. Annelida taxa detected using the Olig01 primers (using the phosphate buffer extraction).

Overall the two methods for extracting DNA with the 18S primers showed similar results in detecting taxa (**Fig. 7**). However, the phosphate buffer method identified two genera and two species that the standard Powersoil Pro DNA-extraction method missed, **including the most common genus in our study, *Fridericia***.

After performing parallel taxonomic assignments of the 18S ASVs recovered by the standard Powersoil Pro DNA-extraction method using both the SILVA and PR2 **reference databases**, we compared their relative performance in resolving Annelid taxonomy. Our analysis revealed that the PR2 database provided substantially higher taxonomic resolution, identifying 11 unique Annelid genera. In contrast, **the SILVA database failed to assign any ASVs at the genus level**, resolving them only to the phylum or class level.

Figure 7. Annelida taxa detected using universal 18S primers compared between different DNA-extraction methods: phosphate buffer (A) and Powersoil Pro (B).

It has to be noted that the Olig01 primers recovered *Fridericia heliota*, which has not been previously recorded in Western Europe according to GBIF data.

3.2.3.1.2. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on species richness

In addition to the observed differences in taxonomic resolution, the relative observed species richness of samples differed substantially between primer sets (Olig01 and 18S; **Fig. 8**). Several significant shifts in species richness rankings of samples were observed, highlighting the extent of change in estimated rankings between the two primers and **underscoring that data from group-specific and so-called universal primers are not directly comparable**. Unfortunately, we cannot determine which species richness ranking is correct.

Figure 8. Observed species richness (OTUs) of Annelida across samples, comparing the Olig01 and 18S primers (18SP) based on the phosphate buffer DNA-extraction method.

The Diepenbeek_LUCAS sample exhibited the most striking change in species richness, rising from a low rank of 27 with the Olig01 primer to the highest rank (1) with the 18SP primer. Similarly, Cerfontaine_LUCAS increased from rank 25 to rank 2, Seneffe_LUCAS from rank 27 to rank 8, and Diepenbeek_0_10 from rank 27 to rank 9. In contrast, Burdinne_10_30 and Cerfontaine_0_10 showed notable declines, dropping from rank 7 to rank 27 and from rank 11 to rank 30, respectively.

When evaluating the variability in estimated species richness based on **18S**, comparing the results obtained using the two different **DNA-extraction methods** (Powersoil Pro and phosphate buffer extraction), estimated species richness was higher using the standard Powersoil Pro DNA-extraction method for most samples (26 out of 31 samples; **Fig. 9**).

Figure 9. Observed species richness (OTUs) of Annelida across samples, based on the 18S primers, comparing the phosphate buffer DNA-extraction method (18SP) and the Powersoil Pro method (18SnoP).

3.2.3.1.3. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on community composition

When evaluating the variability in estimated community composition across identical samples and comparing results derived from both primer sets and DNA-extraction methods, we found that, in general, samples from the same location or land-use category, taken with different sampling protocols, tend to cluster more closely together when using the Olig01 primers, than when using the universal 18S primers (**Fig. 10-12**). This suggests that the group-specific primers better capture community composition patterns, as it reflects the expectation that samples from the same location or land-use category share more similar species compositions than those from different locations or land-use

categories. When using the 18SnoP dataset (based on standard Powersoil Pro DNA-extraction), however, differences between identical samples were most apparent. For example, the Deurne_0_10 sample did not cluster with Deurne_10_30, Cerfontaine_LUCAS did not cluster with Cerfontaine_0_10, and Marke_10_30 did not cluster with Marke0_10, a differentiation not observed in the other two datasets. Moreover, notable disparities were evident in the 18Snp dataset. For instance, Bredene_LUCAS exhibited less clustering with Bredene_0_10 compared to the Olig01 dataset, and Marke_LUCAS showed reduced clustering with the other two Marke samples compared to the Olig01 dataset. Overall, these results might suggest that using only 0.2 g of soil for DNA-extraction, and using universal eukaryotic primers not originally designed for soil-dwelling and soil-surface invertebrates, does not provide a representative view of community composition.

Figure 10. PCoA plot of Annelida (Olig01) based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

Figure 11. PCoA plot of Annelida based on the 18S primers and phosphate buffer DNA-extracts (18SP), using Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

Figure 12. PCoA plot of Annelida based on the 18S primers and Powersoil Pro DNA-extracts (18SnoP), using Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

3.2.3.2. Sampling protocol

3.2.3.2.1. Effect of sampling protocol on species detection

When we focus on the eleven known **Lumbricidae** species recovered in the nine locations for which we have data from all three sampling protocols (**Fig. 13, Table S4**), the species detected in the highest number of samples across all protocols is *Allolobophora chlorotica* (seven locations, 17 samples), followed by *Aporrectodea rosea* (seven locations, 16 samples) and *Aporrectodea longa* (five locations, 12 samples). On the other hand, species like *Bimastos rubidus*, *Satchellius mammalis*, *Lumbricus castaneus*, and *Eiseniella tetraedra* were detected only once (one location, and using only one sampling protocol). Both the INBO_0_10 and LUCAS protocols detected the most species, with nine out of the total 11 known Lumbricidae species recovered in this dataset. The INBO_10_30 sampling protocol detected only six of these species. The INBO_0_10 protocol detected these species in the highest number of samples, with a total of 29 occurrences. Using the LUCAS protocol, we observed a total of 27 occurrences, while

INBO_10_30 detected these species only 19 times. When combining both INBO protocols, these species were detected with a total of 31 occurrences. It is noteworthy that there are two samples in which Lumbricidae are entirely absent (Diepenbeek_0_10 and Diepenbeek_10_30), with very low read count in Diepenbeek_LUCAS. In general, the Lumbricidae species exhibited similar prevalence patterns across sampling protocols, with **differences in species detection more pronounced between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30** than between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS. This pattern held for both dominant and rare species, with some rare species detected exclusively by INBO_0_10 or LUCAS, while none were recorded using INBO_10_30, **suggesting that the deeper 10-30 cm soil layer provides little additional value for detecting Lumbricidae based on eDNA.**

Figure 13. Prevalence of the 11 Lumbricidae species identified in this study per sampling method (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

When we focus on the 30 known **Enchytraeidae** species recovered in the nine locations for which we have data from all three sampling protocols (**Fig. 14, Table S5**), the species detected in the highest number of samples across all protocols is *Fridericia christeri* (eight locations, 20 samples), followed by *Enchytraeus christenseni* (six locations, 16 samples), *Fridericia heliota* (seven locations, 15 samples), *Fridericia galba* (seven locations, 15 samples), and *Enchytraeus buchholzi* (seven locations, 15 samples). Several species such as *Achaeta bifollicula*, *Achaeta bohémica*, and *Achaeta unibulba* were consistently recovered in the samples they were detected, regardless of sampling protocol. On the other hand, species like *Fridericia sohlenii*, *Mesenchytraeus armatus*, and *Oconnorella tubifera* were detected only once (one location, and using only one sampling protocol).

The LUCAS protocol detected the most Enchytraeidae species (28 out of 30), followed by INBO_0_10 (26 out of 30) and INBO_10_30 (21 out of 30). However, when combining both INBO protocols, they detected as many Enchytraeidae species as the LUCAS sampling protocol (28 out of 30). The INBO_0_10 protocol detected these species in the highest number of samples, with a total of 72 occurrences. Using the LUCAS protocol, we observed a total of 61 occurrences, while the INBO_10_30 sampling protocol detected these species an additional 46 times across all samples. When combining both INBO protocols, these species were detected with a total of 79 occurrences.

Overall, **Enchytraeidae species exhibited less similar prevalence patterns across sampling protocols compared to the Lumbricidae**, with larger differences in prevalence of species between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30. *Fridericia galba*, one of the dominant species, was almost completely missed by INBO_10_30 across all locations. Prevalence estimates based on INBO_10_30 were generally lower than those from INBO_0_10, except for *Fridericia heliota* and *Fridericia nemoralis*, **suggesting that the deeper 10-30 cm soil layer provides little additional value for detecting enchytraeids based on eDNA.**

Figure 14. Prevalence of the 30 Enchytraeidae species identified in this study per sampling method (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

Across various locations, species such as *Lumbricus rubellus*, *Fridericia galba* and *Lumbricus castaneus* are frequently detected using INBO_0_10 but not LUCAS. Conversely, species like *Fridericia sohlenii* and *Buchholzia fallax* are often detected by LUCAS but not by INBO_0_10. There are species detected using INBO_0_10 but not INBO_10_30, including *Allolobophora chlorotica*, *Enchytraeus buchholzi*, *Henlea perpusilla* and *Marionina communis*, while very few species are detected by INBO_10_30 that are not found by INBO_0_10, such as *Buchholzia fallax*, *Fridericia nemoralis* and *Fridericia heliota*.

3.2.3.2.2. Unique and shared taxa per sampling protocol

INBO_0_10 detected the highest number of unique known species with a mean of 2.11 and a total of 19. LUCAS detected the second-highest number of unique species with a mean of 1.00 and a total of 9, while INBO_10_30 detected the fewest unique species with a mean of 0.33 and a total of 3 (**Fig. 15**). The differences between protocols were statistically significant (Friedman test $p = 0.0065$). The pairwise comparison between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 was statistically significant ($p = 0.022$), indicating a notable difference in detection rates between these two protocols. INBO_0_10 detected more unique species (mean = 3, total = 27) compared to LUCAS (mean = 1.56, total = 14). The Wilcoxon test showed a p-value of 0.055, indicating a trend towards statistical significance. LUCAS detected significantly more unique species (mean = 4.33, total = 39) compared to INBO_10_30 (mean = 1.22, total = 11). The Wilcoxon test showed a significant difference with a p-value of 0.03. When combining both INBO protocols, INBO detected significantly more unique species (mean = 3.33, total = 30) compared to LUCAS (mean = 1.00, total = 9). The Wilcoxon test showed a significant difference with a p-value of 0.009.

Figure 15. Boxplot illustrating the number of unique Annelida species detected (based on Olig01) per sampling location for each sampling protocol.

In the examination of **relative read abundances** between sampling protocols **per location**, our analysis revealed noteworthy disparities (**Fig. 16, 17**). For instance, several species were notably present in the data from the INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30 sampling protocols, but absent in the data from the LUCAS sampling protocol. In Sombrefe, the relative read abundance of *Allolobophora chlorotica* was high for INBO_0_10 (16.93%) and INBO_10_30 (14.66%), but the species remained undetected using the LUCAS sampling protocol. Similarly, reads identified as *Aporrectodea longa* in Genappe were quite abundant in INBO_0_10 (11.88%) and detected in INBO_10_30 (0.16%), yet absent in LUCAS. In Burdinne, *Fridericia christeri* was represented to a considerable extent in INBO_0_10 (7.81%) and INBO_10_30 (4.05%), without any detection in LUCAS. Vice versa, some OTUs were also notably represented in the LUCAS sampling protocol but absent in both the INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 protocols. For example, in Molenbeek, *Mesenchytraeus otu146* was detected using the LUCAS protocol (14.67%), but was not recorded in either INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30. Similarly, *Aporrectodea otu81* in Molenbeek was present in LUCAS (12.98%) but absent in the two INBO protocols. Overall, there were 26 species that were absent in the LUCAS sampling protocol and relatively abundant, with more than 1% relative read abundance, in at least one of the other two protocols, INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30.

Figure 16. Barplot showing the relative read abundance of the top 11 OTUs for each sampling location and sampling protocol (LUCAS, INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30).

Figure 17. Barplot showing the relative read abundance of the top 11 identified species for each sampling location and sampling protocol (LUCAS, INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30).

3.2.3.2.3. Forest floor vs mineral soil

In **Diepenbeek**, the forest floor sampling protocol recovered the highest amount of unique genetic diversity, with **29% of Annelida OTUs uniquely detected in the forest floor**. Additionally, 37% of all annelid taxa were only detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 29% unique to forest floor and 8% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10). Interestingly, no OTUs were shared between the forest floor and mineral soil sampling protocols. Meanwhile 25% of all OTUs was recovered by all three mineral soil sampling protocols, but not in the forest floor. This indicates **substantially different genetic diversity can be recovered in both the forest floor vs mineral soil**.

In **Gontrode**, the forest floor sampling protocol recovered the highest amount of unique genetic diversity, with 17% of annelid taxa uniquely detected in the forest floor. Additionally, 72% of all annelid taxa were detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 17% unique to forest floor, 33% shared with INBO_0_10, and 22% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10). Interestingly, 22% of taxa were shared among all three protocols, while no taxa were uniquely detected by INBO_10_30, indicating that **the INBO_10_30 protocol did not contribute additional unique biodiversity**.

Table S15 reports the list of Annelida species and genera uniquely detected in the forest floor using Olig01.

3.2.3.2.4. Effect of sampling protocol on species richness and diversity

Figure 18. Observed species richness (*Olig01* Annelida OTUs) based on each sampling protocol, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

For six out of nine sampled locations, estimated **species richness** (Fig. 18) was higher when samples were taken using the INBO_0_10 protocol, compared to the LUCAS protocol (with an average difference of 8.4 OTUs (range: 4 to 11)) and compared to the INBO_10_30 protocol (with an average difference of 10.2 OTUs (range: 4 to 18)). For the two locations where estimated species diversity was higher using the LUCAS protocol, estimated species diversity was highest when the INBO_10_30 protocol was used. Analysis of observed species richness for Annelida across the three sampling protocols revealed no significant differences (Friedman test: $\chi^2 = 1.07$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.587$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction identified no significant differences between any of the protocols: INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.466$), INBO_0_10 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.323$), and INBO_10_30 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.466$). Effect sizes for these comparisons were moderate for INBO_0_10 vs LUCAS ($d = 0.66$) and INBO_0_10 vs INBO_10_30 ($d = 0.47$), and small for INBO_10_30 vs LUCAS ($d = -0.35$). The moderate effect size between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30,

despite identical subsample numbers (16), **suggests that depth has a greater effect on community differences than sampling intensity**. This is supported by the similar effect size when comparing INBO_0_10 to LUCAS, and minimal differences between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS, despite different subsample numbers (16 vs 5). The relative species richness and Shannon diversity index of locations differed substantially between sampling protocols. Several shifts in richness and diversity rankings were observed (**Fig. 18, 19**). The highest average rank change was observed between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS (2.63 positions), followed by INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 (2.13 positions), and the lowest average rank change was observed between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS (0.50 positions).

The observed differences in relative species richness rankings of locations underscore the impact that sampling methodologies can have on the assessment of soil biodiversity. These rank changes mean that the sampling protocol has a profound effect and you **cannot compare data from different sampling protocols. This also suggests that different sampling depths recover different species** (and not only more or less). If not, rankings would be more similar (even if one protocol consistently recovers higher richness).

Figure 19. Shannon diversity index (based on Olig01 Annelida OTUs) across different sampling protocols, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

With the exception of cropland samples, richness and diversity (Shannon) were lowest in samples taken using the INBO_10_30 protocol. Species richness was highest in samples taken using the INBO_0_10 protocol, and Shannon diversity was highest for both INBO_0_10 and LUCAS (**Fig. 20, 21**). The biggest difference in richness and diversity between sampling protocols was observed in grasslands and recreation. Both richness and diversity was highest in recreation, and diversity was lower in forests compared to croplands and grasslands.

Figure 20. Observed species richness (*Annelida* OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

Figure 21. Shannon diversity index (based on *Annelida* OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

3.2.3.2.5. Effect of sampling protocol on community composition

PCoA ordinations based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities computed from CLR-transformed data, show that samples from the same location, but collected using different sampling protocols, cluster more closely together in the two forest locations and one recreation location, and thus are similar in community composition, but less so in two of the four grassland locations (Cerfontaine and Seneffe) and two of the four cropland locations (Genappe and Sombrefe) (**Fig. 10**).

The examination of **relative read abundances** between sampling protocols also revealed noteworthy disparities. In Seneffe, *Allolobophora chlorotica* showed a higher percentage in INBO_0_10 (31.47%) compared to LUCAS (0.67%). In Bredene, two species demonstrated significant variations: *Aporrectodea caliginosa* (30.29% using INBO_0_10, vs 0.07% using LUCAS), and *Henlea andreae* (32.03% using LUCAS, vs 2.31% using INBO_0_10). Genappe's *Fridericia sylvatica* also showed a notable difference (31.35% using LUCAS, vs 1.96% using INBO_0_10). In Marke, *Fridericia isseli* had a higher relative read abundance in LUCAS (25.64%) than in INBO_0_10 (0.59%). Burdinne's *Fridericia galba* exhibited a 24.92% higher relative read abundance in INBO_0_10 (27.86%) compared to LUCAS (2.93%).

When comparing the results of the LUCAS protocol and the INBO_0_10 protocol **per land-use type**, notable differences in the detected species communities (in terms of abundance and community composition) were observed. *Allolobophora chlorotica*, the most abundant species under the INBO_0_10 protocol for the **grassland** samples, experienced a pronounced reduction of 22.5% in relative read abundance when using the LUCAS protocol. On the other hand, the read abundance of *Fridericia otu620* increased significantly (19.6%) when using the LUCAS protocol, becoming the most abundant species instead across all grassland samples.

If we identify the top species exhibiting the most significant differences in relative read abundances across the three sampling protocols **across the complete dataset**, significant variability was observed, along with notable differences in which protocols they were most abundant. *Lumbricus terrestris* had the highest read abundance in INBO_10_30 (79.34%), followed by LUCAS (2.55%). *Achaeta bifollicula* was most abundant in the LUCAS protocol (66.46%), followed by INBO_10_30 (45.91%) and INBO_0_10 (21.66%). *Aporrectodea nocturna* showed its highest read abundance in INBO_0_10 (70.98%), with a minimal amount of reads detected using INBO_10_30 (1.40%).

3.3. Collembola

3.3.1. Summary

The Collembola-specific primers identified 148 Collembola OTUs, which were classified as Entomobryomorpha (54 OTUs), Poduromorpha (23 OTUs), Neelipleona (16 OTUs) and Symphypleona (nine OTUs). 80 OTUs were identified at the genus level, and 28 OTUs at the species level. *Megalothorax* was the most abundant genus, representing 16.71% of the total reads. Other abundant genera included *Isotomurus*, *Mesaphorura*, *Tullbergia*, *Entomobrya*, *Parisotoma* and *Pogonognathellus*. The most abundant species were *Megalothorax incertus* (10.73%), *Isotomurus maculatus* (4.89%), and *Megalothorax willemi* (3.14%). The OTUs that remained unclassified at the species or genus level however also included some of the most abundant OTUs across the complete dataset.

In the comparison between **molecular analysis protocols**, the Collembola-specific primers (Coll01) identified **21 genera** and 17 species **that were not identified when using the universal 18S primers**. Notably, this included the most abundant genus (based on Coll01), *Megalothorax*, and the most abundant species, *Megalothorax incertus*. The phosphate buffer DNA-extraction method (18SP) identified a greater number of unique genera and species than the Powersoil Pro method (18SnoP).

In terms of richness (OTUs), the rankings were similar between the Collembola-specific primers and the 18S primers. When analyzing community composition, samples from the same location, but taken with different sampling protocols, tended to have a more similar community composition than samples from different locations when using the Collembola-specific primers (Coll01) than with the universal 18S primers.

When comparing the performance of the Collembola-specific primers across the **three sampling protocols** (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, and LUCAS), the results showed that the INBO_0_10 protocol generally outperformed the other two in detecting unique species. Specifically, INBO_0_10 detected a higher number of unique species across most locations, although the differences were not always statistically significant. However, species richness and diversity were consistently higher in samples processed with the INBO_0_10 protocol, particularly in forest samples. **The forest floor sampling protocol recovered the highest unique genetic diversity and, together with the INBO_0_10 protocol, accounted for most detected OTUs.** Estimated species richness and Shannon diversity were higher with

the INBO_0_10 protocol compared to INBO_10_30 in six out of eight locations and compared to LUCAS in all eight locations. A significant difference in Collembola richness was observed between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.039$, $d = 1.10$), representing the largest effect size across sampling protocol comparisons. With the exception of cropland samples, richness and diversity (Shannon) were highest in samples taken using the INBO_0_10 protocol. **The largest differences in richness between sampling protocols occurred in forests**, while diversity differences were most pronounced in grasslands. Both richness and diversity was highest in forests. Overall, the analyses suggest that depth has a more profound effect than sampling intensity on the Collembola diversity captured, and that the **combination of surface sampling and higher subsample number recovers the highest diversity** of all three sampling protocols tested.

3.3.2. General

Illumina sequencing yielded a total of 5,887,234 reads for the Coll01 primers. Following quality control and filtering, the number of reads per sample ranged from 31,697 to 212,322, with an average of 116,773 reads per sample. One sample (Seneffe_0_10) yielded only 844 reads and was excluded from subsequent analyses.

A total of 198 OTUs were identified across 35 samples (Seneffe_0_10 included), including 148 Collembola OTUs. The remaining OTUs comprised ten Annelida OTUs and 27 Insecta OTUs. The 148 Collembola OTUs were classified as Entomobryomorpha (54 OTUs), Poduromorpha (23 OTUs), Neelipleona (16 OTUs) and Symphypleona (nine OTUs). A total of 46 Collembola OTUs (31.1%) remained unclassified at the order level. Of the 102 classified OTUs, **80 were identified at the genus level**, and **28** of these were further **identified at the species level (Table S6, Fig. 22)**.

After correcting for uneven sequencing depth per sample, these orders collectively accounted for 59.52% of total sequence reads (Entomobryomorpha: 33.07%, Neelipleona: 16.71%, Poduromorpha: 7.59%, Symphypleona: 2.15%), while the unclassified OTUs accounted for the remaining 40.48%.

Megalothorax was the most abundant genus (16.71%), while other known genera include *Isotomurus* (4.89%), *Mesaphorura* (3.27%), *Tullbergia* (2.40%), *Entomobrya* (2.38%), *Parisotoma* (2.26%), *Pogonognathellus* (1.85%), *Heteromurus* (1.80%), *Scutisotoma* (1.43%) and *Willowsia* (1.38%). Other OTUs classified at the genus level were each represented by less than 1% of total reads.

The most abundant OTU across all samples was *Megalothorax incertus*, accounting for 10.73% of total reads, followed by Isotomidae OTU190 (9.36%), Collembola OTU1060 (9.02%), Collembola OTU493 (5.96%), Collembola OTU2 (5.68%), Collembola OTU5 (5.68%), *Isotomurus maculatus* (4.89%), Collembola OTU531 (4.07%), *Megalothorax willemi* (3.14%), Entomobryomorpha OTU182 (2.35%), *Parisotoma* OTU641 (2.25%), *Entomobrya* OTU681 (2.14%) and *Pogonognathellus* OTU76 (1.69%). Other identified species include *Protaphorura armata* (1.31%). All other known species each accounted for less than 1% of total reads.

The most prevalent OTUs across all 11 sampled locations were Isotomidae OTU1784 (present at all 11 locations), followed by Collembola OTU1060, *Entomobrya* OTU681 and Entomobryidae OTU1874 (present at nine locations each) and Collembola OTU1060 (present at eight locations). Collembola OTU5 and *Megalothorax willemi* were detected at seven of these locations, while *Willowsia nigromaculata* and *Folsomia candida* were observed at six locations. *Megalothorax incertus*, the most abundant species, was detected at five locations, along with *Isotomurus maculatus* and seven other unidentified OTUs. The other highly abundant OTUs were found in four or less locations.

Figure 22. Krona plot visualizing all Collembola taxa (based on Coll01). Each ring in the plot represents a hierarchical level (class - order - family - genus - species/OTU). The size of the segments reflects the relative read abundance of each taxon across the complete dataset.

Species detection using these group-specific primers (Coll01) also seems to align with known habitat preferences for specific species. *Megalothorax minimus* for example is considered a true forest species (Heiniger *et al.*, 2015) and was only detected in the forest locations included in the study (**Table S8**).

Overall the two **methods for extracting DNA** used with the 18S primers (Powersoil Pro, 18SnoP, and phosphate buffer, 18SP) showed more similar results in detecting species and genera (**Fig. 24**; 18SP: 16 genera and 14 species; 18SnoP: 11 genera and 11 species). However, the phosphate buffer method identified six genera (*Papirinus*, *Xenylla*, *Friesea*, *Willowsia*, *Tomocerus*, *Orchessela*) that the standard Powersoil Pro method missed, while the latter detected only one additional genus (*Pogonognathellus*). The phosphate buffer method also identified seven species (*Parisotoma prodigiosa*, *Xenylla grisea*, *Friesea japonica*, *Isotomurus palustris*, *Willowsia nigromaculata*, *Folsomia candida*) that were not detected by the Powersoil Pro method. In contrast, the Powersoil Pro method identified only two additional species (*Pogonognathellus flavescens* and *Heteromurus major*).

Figure 24. Collembola taxa detected using universal 18S primers compared between different DNA-extraction methods: phosphate buffer (A) and Powersoil Pro (B).

The Collembola-specific primers (Coll01) identified two species, *Tomocerus jilinensis* and *Tomocerus nigrus*, along with one genus, *Dicranocentrus*, that had **not been previously recorded in Western Europe, based on GBIF data**. Similarly, the universal 18S primers detected four species: *Tullbergia yosii*, *Onychiurus hangchowensis*, *Friesea japonica*, and *Papirinus prodigiosus* as well as one genus, *Papirinus*, none of which have been previously documented in Western Europe according to GBIF records. This adds to the question whether or not species-level identifications can be trusted.

After performing parallel taxonomic assignments of 18S ASVs using both the SILVA and PR2 **reference databases**, we compared their relative performance in resolving Collembola taxonomy. Our analysis revealed that the PR2 database provided substantially higher taxonomic resolution, identifying 16 unique Collembola genera. In contrast, **the SILVA database failed to assign any ASVs at the genus level**, resolving them only to the class level.

3.3.3.1.2. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on species richness

The richness rankings (based on OTUs) are generally similar across the three molecular analysis protocols (**Fig. 25**), with some notable exceptions. For example, the rank of Molenbeek_10_30 increased significantly from 28th (Coll01) to 6th (18SP) and 3rd (18SnoP), while Cerfontaine_0-10 declined from 8th (Coll01) to 26th (18SP) and 23rd (18SnoP). Similarly, Burdinne_10_30 dropped from 8th (Coll01) to 31st (18SP) and 23rd (18SnoP). Overall, 18SnoP yielded higher species richness compared to 18SP in 26 out of 31 samples, with an average increase of six OTUs.

Figure 25. Observed species richness (OTUs) of *Collembola* across samples, comparing the Coll01 and 18S primers, and for the latter also comparing the phosphate buffer extraction method (18SP) with the Powersoil Pro method (18SnoP).

3.3.3.1.3. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on community composition

When evaluating the variability in estimated community composition across identical soil samples and comparing results derived from both primersets and DNA-extraction methods, we found that, in general, samples from the same location or land-use category, taken with different sampling protocols, tend to cluster more closely together when using the Coll01 primers, than when using the universal 18S primers (**Fig. 26-28**). This suggests that the group-specific primers better capture community composition

patterns, as it reflects the expectation that samples from the same location or land-use category share more similar community compositions than those from different locations or land-use categories.

Figure 26. PCoA plot of *Collembola* (*Coll01*) based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

Figure 27. PCoA plot of *Collembola* based on the 18S primers and phosphate buffer DNA-extracts (18SP), using Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

Figure 28. PCoA plot of *Collembola* based on the 18S primers and Powersoil Pro DNA-extracts (18SnoP), using Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

3.3.3.2. Sampling protocol

3.3.3.2.1. Effect of sampling protocol on species detection

When we focus on the 25 known *Collembola* species recovered in the 9 locations for which we have data from all three sampling protocols (**Fig. 29, Table S8**), the species detected in the highest number of samples across all protocols is *Megalothorax willemi* (7 locations, 14 samples), followed by *Folsomia candida* (4 locations, 4 samples) and *Willowsia nigromaculata* (3 locations, 6 samples). On the other hand, species like *Desoria tigrina*, *Lipothrix lubbocki* and *Neanura muscorum* were detected only once (one location, and using only one sampling protocol).

The INBO_0_10 protocol detected the most species, with 21 out of the total 25 known *Collembola* species recovered in this dataset, followed by LUCAS with 20, and INBO_10_30 with 15. The INBO_0_10 protocol detected these species in the highest number of samples, with a total of 41 occurrences. Using the LUCAS protocol, we observed a total of 28 occurrences, while INBO_10_30 detected these species 27 times.

Species such as *Megalothorax incertus*, *Isotomurus maculatus* and *Folsomia candida* were detected across multiple locations and methods. In general, across all locations, species prevalence patterns across sampling protocols were more similar between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS, than between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30. Some species were detected exclusively by INBO_0_10 and/or LUCAS, while none were recorded exclusively using INBO_10_30. (**Table S8, Fig. 29**), suggesting that **the deeper 10-30 cm soil layer provides little additional value for detecting Collembola based on eDNA.**

Figure 29. Prevalence of the 25 Collembola species identified in this study per sampling method (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

3.3.3.2.2. Unique and shared taxa per sampling protocol

INBO_0_10 detected the **highest number of unique species** (mean = 1.63, total = 13), followed by INBO_10_30 (mean = 0.75, total = 6) and LUCAS (mean = 0.5, total = 4) (**Fig. 30**). Although there is a trend suggesting that INBO_0_10 detects more unique species, the differences are not statistically significant (Friedman test, $p = 0.13$). The most notable comparison is between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS, where INBO_0_10 detected more unique species (mean = 2.0, total = 18) compared to LUCAS (mean = 1.0, total = 9), although the Wilcoxon test indicated no significant difference ($p = 0.26$). LUCAS detected slightly more unique species (mean = 1.78, total = 16) compared to INBO_10_30 (mean = 1.22, total = 11), although the difference was again not statistically significant (Wilcoxon test, $p = 0.72$). The INBO_0_10 protocol however showed a moderate-to-large effect size when compared to LUCAS (Cohen's $d = 0.77$, $p = 0.09$, Holm-adjusted $p = 0.27$). In contrast, the INBO_10_30 protocol showed only a small effect size when compared to LUCAS (Cohen's $d = 0.13$, Holm-adjusted $p = 0.78$). The comparison between the two INBO protocols (0-10 cm vs. 10-30 cm) showed a small-to-moderate effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.37$, $p = 0.34$, Holm-adjusted $p = 0.68$). While none of the comparisons reached statistical significance after controlling for multiple comparisons using the Holm correction, the effect size calculations suggest that the INBO_0_10 protocol may be more effective at detecting species compared to both LUCAS and INBO_10_30 protocols.

When combining both INBO protocols, the total number of unique species detected by INBO was higher (mean = 2.67, total = 24) compared to LUCAS (mean = 0.78, total = 7). Nonetheless, the Wilcoxon test again did not report a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.07$).

At all locations except for Marke, **more species were uniquely detected** by one of the INBO sampling protocols than by the LUCAS sampling protocol. In general, each location had specific species uniquely identified by either the INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30 method, which were not captured by LUCAS. The highest number of unique species detected by the INBO methods was observed at Diepenbeek and Genappe. Marke, however, stood out as an exception: LUCAS detected multiple species missed by both INBO sampling methods and a notable number of species that were detected using INBO_0_10, were absent when using INBO_10_30.

Interestingly, INBO_0_10 detected several species that were not captured by LUCAS across multiple locations (**Table S8**), including *Willowsia nigromaculata* and *Megalothorax willemi*. In contrast, LUCAS

rarely detected species not identified by either INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30. Exceptions to this trend include *Neanura muscorum*, *Orchesella villosa* and *Entomobrya lanuginosa*, which were each detected at only one location. A similar trend was observed when considering all OTUs, with often stronger overlap between LUCAS and INBO_0_10 compared to LUCAS and INBO_10_30.

Figure 30. Boxplot illustrating the number of unique Collembola species detected (based on Coll01) per sampling location for each sampling protocol.

In the examination of **relative read abundances** between sampling protocols per location, our analysis revealed noteworthy disparities (Fig. 31, 32, Fig. S2). For instance, several species were notably represented when using the INBO_0_10 or INBO_10_30 sampling protocols, but absent when using the LUCAS protocol. In Burdinne, *Isotomurus maculatus* had a high relative read abundance of 53.56% using the INBO_0_10 protocol, but only 0.01% using INBO_10_30, while remaining undetected using the LUCAS sampling protocol. A similar trend was observed in Sombrefe, where *Isotomurus maculatus* was prevalent at 40.90% using INBO_0_10, yet absent when using both INBO_10_30 and LUCAS protocols.

Figure 31. Barplot showing the relative read abundance of the top 11 OTUs for each sampling location and sampling protocol (LUCAS, INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30).

Figure 32. Barplot showing the relative read abundance of the top 11 identified species for each sampling location and sampling protocol (LUCAS, INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30).

3.3.3.2.3. Forest floor vs mineral soil

When considering all OTUs, the forest floor sampling protocol in Diepenbeek recovered the highest proportion of uniquely detected Collembola taxa among all protocols, with 11% of Collembola OTUs uniquely detected in the forest floor. Additionally, 42% of all OTUs were detected exclusively by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols, combining 11% unique to forest floor, 24% shared exclusively between forest floor and INBO_0_10, and 7% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10. Species found only in the forest floor but not in the top 10 cm of soil (INBO_0_10) include *Allacma fusca*, *Orchesella villosa*, and *Willowsia nigromaculata*. Additionally, species detected in the forest floor but absent from both INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 include *Geophilus truncorum*, *Thrips hawaiiensis*, *Othius subuliformis*, *Oodinychus ovalis*, *Nargus algericus*, *Campylomyza flavipes*, *Hilara maura* and *Helina impuncta*.

In Gontrode, the forest floor sampling protocol also recovered the highest amount of unique genetic diversity, with **29% of Collembola OTUs uniquely detected in the forest floor**. Furthermore, 69% of all OTUs were detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols, which includes 29% unique to forest floor, 37% shared with INBO_0_10, and 3% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10. Interestingly, no OTUs were uniquely recovered by the INBO_10_30 sampling protocol, indicating that **the INBO_10_30 protocol did not contribute additional unique biodiversity**.

Table S15 reports the list of Collembola species and genera uniquely detected in the forest floor using Coll01.

3.3.3.2.4. Effect of sampling protocol on species richness and diversity

At five out of eight locations, species richness and diversity (Shannon index) were higher when samples were collected using the INBO_0_10 protocol compared to the INBO_10_30 protocol (with an average difference of 9.8 OTUs (range: 4 to 25)) (**Fig. 33, 34**). For all eight locations, species richness was higher with the INBO_0_10 protocol compared to the LUCAS protocol (with an average difference of 4.1 OTUs (range: 1 to 11)), and for seven out of eight locations, the Shannon diversity index also showed higher values for INBO_0_10. Analysis of observed species richness for Collembola across the three sampling protocols revealed a marginally non-significant difference (Friedman test: $\chi^2 = 5.43$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.066$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction identified a **significant difference between the INBO_0_10 and LUCAS protocols** ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.039$, $d = 1.1$), while no significant differences were observed between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.7$)

or between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.78$). Effect sizes for these comparisons were large for INBO_0_10 vs LUCAS ($d = 1.1$), moderate for INBO_0_10 vs INBO_10_30 ($d = 0.48$) and small for INBO_10_30 vs LUCAS ($d = -0.18$). The large effect size observed between the INBO_0_10 and LUCAS protocols suggests that they may yield systematically different estimates of species richness for Collembola. Moreover, compared to the moderate effect between soil layers ($d = 0.48$), it suggests that **both depth and sampling intensity influence Collembola richness, with the combination of surface sampling and higher subsample number yielding substantially higher richness** results.

Additionally, the relative species richness and Shannon diversity index of locations differed substantially between sampling protocols. Several shifts in richness and diversity rankings were observed. The most notable change occurred at the Diepenbeek location, where the INBO_0_10 protocol recorded the highest species richness, while the INBO_10_30 protocol resulted in the second lowest. Similarly, samples from Cerfontaine and Genappe exhibited significant changes in their Shannon diversity index rankings across different sampling protocols. The highest average rank change was observed between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 (3.14 positions), followed by INBO_10_30 and LUCAS (2.14 positions), and the lowest average rank change was observed between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS (1 position).

Figure 33. Observed species richness (Coll01 Collembola OTUs) based on each sampling protocol, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

Figure 34. Shannon diversity index (based on Coll01 Collembola OTUs) across different sampling protocols, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

With the exception of the cropland samples, species richness was highest in samples analysed using the INBO_0_10 protocol. In forests, the INBO_0_10 protocol was followed by the LUCAS protocol and the INBO_10_30 protocol, while for grasslands and recreation, LUCAS and INBO_10_30 showed comparable (low) values (**Fig. 35**). The same trend was observed for diversity (Shannon index), with the exception of recreational grassland, where all three sampling protocols showed similar values (**Fig. 36**). For species richness the biggest difference between sampling protocols was observed in forests, while for Shannon diversity it was in grasslands. Based on the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol, **richness and Shannon diversity increased towards the less intensively managed ecosystems**, with the highest values recorded in forests. **Using LUCAS, this was only the case, and less pronounced**, for richness, while in grasslands, Shannon diversity was lower compared to croplands instead of higher. In contrast, **the INBO_10_30 sampling protocol failed to capture such a pattern**, and richness was similar across all land-use types, and Shannon diversity decreased towards the less intensively managed ecosystems.

Figure 35. Observed species richness (*Coll01* Collembola OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

Figure 36. Shannon diversity index (based on *Coll01* Collembola OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

3.3.3.2.5. Effect of sampling protocol on community composition

PCoA ordinations based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities computed from CLR-transformed data, show no systematic differences or similarities between the LUCAS, INBO_0_10, and INBO_10_30 sampling methods. At some locations, species composition was more similar between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30, while at others, it was more similar between LUCAS and INBO_0_10. Samples from the same location, but collected with different sampling protocols, tended to cluster more together for the forests and recreation plot(s), and thus are similar in community composition, than for the cropland and grassland samples (**Fig. 26**).

3.4. Arthropoda

3.4.1. Summary

Insecta and Arachnida, the main focus of these primers, accounted for 31.11% and 10% of the genetic diversity recovered, respectively, and only 9.79% and 2.49% of the reads recovered, respectively. Among the 137 non-Collembola Arthropoda OTUs, diversity was dominated by Insecta (84 OTUs), Arachnida (27 OTUs), Chilopoda (6 OTUs) and Malacostraca (5 OTUs). **Coleoptera and mites** (Mesostigmata and Acari) **were the most diverse and abundant** soil-dwelling orders detected. The Curculionidae family (**weevils**) showed the highest genetic diversity in our dataset, followed by Elateridae (click beetles), Macrochelidae (predatory mites), Discourellidae (soft-winged flower beetles), Ixodidae (hard ticks), and Pemphigidae (woolly aphids). *Amphimallon solstitiale* (European chafer) was the most abundant species, comprising 20% of Arthropoda reads. 85% of OTUs could be identified at the family level, 46% at the genus level, and 31% at the species level.

In the comparison between **molecular analysis protocols**, Arthropoda-specific primers (Inse01) and universal eukaryotic primers (18S) showed complementary detection patterns. Inse01 uniquely identified four orders and 25 families, including abundant genera such as *Amphimallon* and *Athous* (based on Inse01), while **18S** uniquely detected two orders and 32 families, **recovering a broader diversity of mites**. **Inse01 was more effective for flying insects** (larvae), **as well as true bugs**, and a broader range of **beetles**. Comparisons of DNA-extraction methods using 18S primers revealed that the phosphate buffer method (18SP) outperformed the Powersoil Pro method (18SnoP), by detecting **22 insect genera that were missed by the standard Powersoil Pro DNA-extraction method**.

When comparing the performance of the Arthropoda-specific primers across the three **sampling protocols** (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, and LUCAS), the results showed that the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol detected the highest number of unique species that were missed by the other sampling protocols, followed by LUCAS in second place, while INBO_10_30 detected the fewest unique species. The differences between protocols were not statistically significant. In addition, the forest floor sampling protocol recovered the most unique genetic diversity, with **44-50% of arthropod taxa uniquely detected in the forest floor**, and 70-81% of all arthropod taxa being detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols. Estimated species richness was higher with the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol compared to LUCAS in 7 out of 9 locations, though pairwise comparisons showed only a

marginally non-significant difference ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.06$). No significant differences were observed between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 or between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS. Arthropod communities exhibited substantial biological differences between surface samples (INBO_0_10) and LUCAS ($d = 1.43$), moderate differences between the INBO soil layers ($d = 0.69$), and negligible differences between deeper INBO_10_30 samples and LUCAS ($d = -0.07$). These findings indicate that **both soil depth and sampling intensity influence arthropod richness**, with surface sampling combined with higher subsampling yielding the greatest richness.

3.4.2. General

After quality control and filtering, Illumina sequencing resulted in a read count from 21,550 to 408,064 reads per sample for the Arthropoda-specific primers (*Inse01*), with an average of 186,597 reads per sample. A total of 270 OTUs were identified, including 63 Collembola, 137 non-Collembola Arthropoda, and 70 Annelida OTUs. Within the non-Collembola Arthropoda, 84 OTUs were identified as Insecta, 27 as Arachnida, six as Chilopoda, five as Malacostraca, and two as Diplura, while 13 OTUs remained unclassified at the class level. (**Table S9, Fig. 37**). **Coleoptera (beetles) and Diptera (flies) were the most diverse** orders detected (34 and 23 OTUs respectively), followed by Mesostigmata (**Acari**; parasitic mites; 17 OTUs), **Hemiptera** (true bugs; nine OTUs), Hymenoptera (ants, bees, and wasps; nine OTUs), Geophilomorpha (soil centipedes; four OTUs), Ixodida (**Acari**; ticks; four OTUs), and Orthoptera (grasshoppers and crickets; two OTUs). Several orders, including Amphipoda (amphipods), are represented by a single OTU. Eight OTUs (two Arachnida, one Chilopoda, one Insecta, and four Malacostraca) remain unclassified at the order level. The **Curculionidae** family (**weevils**) showed the **highest genetic diversity in our dataset** with seven OTUs detected, followed by Elateridae (click beetles) and Macrochelidae (predatory mites), each with five OTUs. Several families, including Chironomidae (non-biting midges), Discourellidae (soft-winged flower beetles), Ixodidae (hard ticks), Pemphigidae (woolly aphids), and Sciaridae (dark-winged fungus gnats), were represented by four OTUs each, while Cecidomyiidae (gall midges), Cicadellidae (leafhoppers), and Hydraenidae (minute moss beetles) each had three OTUs. Numerous families were represented by only two or one OTU. 18 OTUs (15%) remained unclassified at the family level. 57 OTUs (46%) could be identified at genus level, of which 38 (31%) could be further identified at species level.

Annelida constitutes 62.8% of the reads, while Arthropoda accounts for 37.2%. Collembola comprised 19.66% of the reads, followed by Insecta at 9.79%, and Arachnida at 2.49%. Chilopoda, Malacostraca, and Diplura each accounted for less than 1% of total reads, while unknown arthropod OTUs accounted for 4.5% of total reads. Out of the total Arthropoda reads, Insecta accounted for 75.13%, Arachnida 19.09%, and Chilopoda, Malacostraca and Diplura respectively 2.89%, 2.20%, and 0.68%. **Coleoptera (61.24%) and Acari (19%) were the most abundant orders in the Arthropoda subset.** Elateridae (click beetles) and Scarabaeidae (scarab beetles) were the most abundant known families, accounting for 22.52% and 20.05% of the Arthropoda reads, followed by Curculionidae (weevils; 9.30%) and Pemphigidae (woolly aphids; 5.30%). All other classified families represented each less than 5% of reads. The OTUs that remained unclassified at the family level accounted for 14%. *Amphimallon* (chafer beetles) and *Athous* (click beetles) were the most abundant genera overall, accounting for 20.05% and 16.64% of the Arthropoda reads respectively, followed by *Polydrusus* (weevils; 4.65%), *Laparocerus* (weevils; 4.27%), *Agriotes* (click beetles; 3.50%), *Nalassus* (darkling beetles; 3.28%), *Nematus* (sawflies; 2.88%), and *Pemphigus* (gall aphids; 2.66%). All other genera each have a percentage of reads lower than 2%.

The most abundant species across all samples is *Amphimallon solstitiale* (European chafer), accounting for 20.05% of Arthropoda reads, followed by *Athous haemorrhoidalis* (click beetle; 16.64%), Acari OTU262 (12.03%), and *Polydrusus cervinus* (green immigrant leaf weevil; 4.64%). The most prevalent OTUs/species across all eleven sampled locations were Lampyridae OTU2671 (fireflies) and Tenthredinidae OTU2355 (common sawflies; 11 locations), followed by *Varroa* OTU3756 (parasitic mite; 10 locations), *Schlechtendalia* OTU413 (woolly gall aphids; nine locations) and Discourellidae OTU4538 (soft-winged flower beetles; seven locations).

Figure 37. Krona plot visualizing all Arthropoda taxa (based on Inse01). Each ring in the plot represents a hierarchical level (Phylum - class - order - family - genus - species/OTU). The size of the segments reflects the relative read abundance of each taxon across the complete dataset.

3.4.3. Effects of different protocols on taxa detection and diversity

3.4.3.1. Molecular analysis protocol

3.4.3.1.1. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on taxa detection

Four orders and 25 families were only identified with the Inse01 primers, while two orders and 32 families were only identified with the 18S primers (**Table S10 and S11**). The Inse01 primers identified 55 genera and 42 species that were not detected when using the universal 18S primers (with the phosphate buffer method used for DNA-extraction; **Table S12 and S13, Fig. 38, Fig. 39**). Notably, this included all genera with an overall read abundance higher than 2% (based on Inse01): *Amphimallon*, *Athous*, *Polydrusus*, *Lapacocerus*, *Agriotes*, *Nematus* and *Pemphigus*, as well as the two most abundant species *Amphimallon solstitiale* and *Athous haemorrhoidalis*.

A total of 46 genera and 39 species were observed with the 18S primers (with the phosphate buffer method used for DNA-extraction) which were not detected with the Inse01 primers.

Only seven genera were identified with both primersets: *Cryptops*, *Geophilus*, *Pseudolycoriella*, *Tipula*, *Strigamia*, *Dendrolaelaps* and *Macrocheles*. No species were detected by both primersets. The **Inse01 dataset demonstrates a greater efficacy in detecting insects**, as evidenced by the detection of many unique families within e.g. Coleoptera (beetles), Diptera (flies), Hemiptera (true bugs), Lepidoptera (butterflies and moths), Orthoptera (grasshoppers and crickets) and Psocoptera (bark lice). Conversely, **18S seems to be better at detecting mites**, within the Sarcoptiformes order, as well as Prostigmata and Trombidiformes mites. 18S also uniquely detected Isopoda (woodlice).

Overall the two methods for extracting DNA with the 18S primers showed similar results in detecting taxa (**Fig. 40**). However, the phosphate buffer method identified 22 genera and 18 species that the standard Powersoil Pro method missed, while, the standard Powersoil Pro method identified eight genera and three species that the phosphate buffer method missed.

It has to be noted that the Inse01 primers identified three species (*Thrips hawaiiensis*, *Nargus algericus*, and *Eupteryx gracilirama*), and three genera (*Schlechtendalia*, *Laparocerus*, and *Lycocerus*), which have not been previously recorded in Europe according to GBIF data. Similarly, the 18S primers detected five species (*Otitesella tsamvi*, *Zatania albimaculata*, *Naiadacarus arboricola*, *Sancassania nesbitti*, and

Pseudacteon obtusus), and two genera (*Otitesella* and *Zatania*), which have not been previously recorded in Europe according to GBIF data.

Figure 38. Arthropoda taxa detected using universal 18S primers and phosphate buffer DNA-extraction, including only the following classes: Insecta, Arachnida, Chilopoda, Diplura, and Malacostraca.

Figure 39. Arthropoda taxa detected using Arthropoda-specific primers (Inse01), including only the following classes: Insecta, Arachnida, Chilopoda, Diplura, and Malacostraca.

Figure 40. Arthropoda taxa detected using universal 18S primers and Powersoil Pro DNA-extraction, including only the following classes: Insecta, Arachnida, Chilopoda, Diplura, and Malacostraca.

3.4.3.1.2. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on species richness

Figure 41. Observed species richness across samples, based on the dataset including all Arthropoda OTUs, comparing the Inse01 and 18S primers, and for the latter also comparing the phosphate buffer extraction method (18SP) with the Powersoil Pro method (18SnoP).

For most samples the rank based on species richness is generally quite similar across the three molecular methods, with some exceptions. For instance, the rank for Sombreffe_0_10 shifted from 24th (Inse01) to 6th (18SP) and 12th (18SnoP), while Cerfontaine_0_10 dropped from 9th (Inse01) to 28th (18SP) and 31st (18SnoP). Similarly, Molenbeek_10_30 rose from 28th (Inse01) to 14th (18SP) and 10th (18SnoP) (Fig. 41).

3.4.3.1.3. Effect of molecular analysis protocol on community composition

When evaluating the variability in estimated community composition across identical soil samples and comparing results derived from both primersets and DNA-extraction methods, we found that, in general, samples from the same location or land-use category, taken with different sampling protocols, tend to cluster more closely together when using the group-specific Inse01 primers, than when using the universal 18S primers (**Fig. 42 - 44**). This suggests that the group-specific primers better capture community composition patterns, as it reflects the expectation that samples from the same location or land-use category share more similar species compositions than those from different locations or land-use categories.

Figure 42. PCoA plot of Arthropoda (Inse01) based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed community data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

Figure 43. PCoA plot of Arthropoda based on the 18S primers and phosphate buffer DNA-extracts (18SP), using Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

Figure 44. PCoA plot of Arthropoda based on the 18S primers and Powersoil Pro DNA-extracts (18SnoP), using Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

3.4.3.2. Sampling protocol

3.4.3.2.1. Effect of sampling protocol on species detection

When we focus on the 29 known arthropods species recovered in the locations for which we have data from all three sampling protocols (**Fig. 45, Table S14**), the species detected in the highest number of samples across all protocols is *Tachyporus nitidulus* (four locations, seven samples), followed by *Trechus quadristriatus* (three locations, five samples) and *Corynoptera perpusilla* (four locations, five samples). On the other hand, species like *Polydrusus cervinus*, *Adrastus rachifer*, *Dilophus febrilis* and *Otiorhynchus ovatus* were detected only once (one location, and using only one sampling protocol).

The INBO_0_10 sampling protocol detected the most species, with 20 out of the total 29 known species recovered in this dataset, followed by LUCAS with 16, and INBO_10_30 with 14 of these species. The INBO_0_10 protocol detected these species in the highest number of samples, with a total of 28 occurrences, followed by LUCAS with 19 occurrences, and INBO_10_30 with 16 occurrences. Species

such as *Corynoptera perpusilla*, *Trechus quadristriatus*, *Tipula varipennis* and *Athous haemorrhoidalis* were uniquely found by INBO, often in the top 0-10 cm soil layer. Meanwhile, species like *Nematopogon swammerdamellus* and *Chorthippus parallelus parallelus* were occasionally detected only by LUCAS. Overall, prevalence estimates based on INBO_10_30 and LUCAS were generally lower than those from inbo_0_10. Many species were detected exclusively by INBO_0_10 and/or LUCAS, while only 3 were exclusively recorded using INBO_10_30, suggesting that **the deeper 10-30 cm soil layer provides little additional value for detecting arthropods based on eDNA.** (Fig. 45, Table S14).

Figure 45. Prevalence of the 29 Arthropoda species identified (using Inse01) in this study per sampling method (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, LUCAS).

3.4.3.2.2. Unique and shared taxa per sampling protocol

Across all sampling protocols, INBO_0_10 detected the highest number of unique species (mean = 1.44, total = 13), LUCAS detected the second-highest (mean = 1.11, total = 10) and INBO_10_30 detected the fewest unique species (mean = 0.44, total = 4) (**Fig. 46, Table S14**). The differences between protocols were however not statistically significant (Friedman test $p = 0.17$). The closest to statistical significance was INBO_0_10 vs INBO_10_30 ($p = 0.089$). Pairwise comparisons between sampling protocols show that INBO_0_10 also detected more unique species (mean = 2.11, total = 19) compared to LUCAS (mean = 1.33, total = 12), although the Wilcoxon test yielded a p -value of 0.26, indicating no significant difference between the protocols for Arthropoda. LUCAS detected slightly more unique species (mean = 1.56, total = 14) compared to INBO_10_30 (mean = 1.11, total = 10), although the difference was again not statistically significant (Wilcoxon test, p -value = 0.6). The combination of both INBO protocols detected significantly more unique species (mean = 2.56, total = 23) compared to LUCAS (mean = 1.11, total = 10) according to the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (p -value = 0.04).

Figure 46. Boxplot illustrating the number of unique Arthropoda species detected (based on Inse01) per sampling location for each sampling protocol.

Figure 47. Barplot showing the relative read abundance of the top 11 Arthropoda OTUs for each sampling location and sampling protocol (LUCAS, INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30).

Figure 48. Barplot showing the relative read abundance of the top 11 identified Arthropoda species for each sampling location and sampling protocol (LUCAS, INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30).

3.4.3.2.3. Forest floor vs mineral soil

When considering all OTUs, the forest floor sampling protocol in Diepenbeek recovered the highest proportion of uniquely detected arthropod taxa among all protocols, with **50% of arthropod taxa uniquely detected in the forest floor**. Additionally, 70% of all arthropod taxa were only detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 50% unique to forest floor, 12% shared exclusively between forest floor and INBO_0_10 and 8% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10).

In Gontrode, the forest floor sampling protocol also recovered the highest amount of unique genetic diversity, with 44% of arthropod taxa uniquely detected in the forest floor. Additionally, 81% of all arthropod taxa were detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 44% unique to forest floor, 25% shared with INBO_0_10 and 12% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10). Interestingly, only 3% of taxa were shared among all three protocols, and only two taxa were uniquely detected by INBO_10_30, indicating the importance of the forest floor and the 0-10 cm layer for capturing soil arthropod biodiversity.

Table S15 reports the list of Arthropoda species and genera uniquely detected in the forest floor using the Inse01 primers.

3.4.3.2.4. Effect of sampling protocol on species richness and diversity

For six out of eight locations, **observed species richness (Fig. 49)** was higher when samples were taken using the INBO_0_10 protocol, compared to the INBO_10_30 protocol (with an average difference of 15.7 OTUs (range: 1 to 32)). For seven out of nine locations, observed species richness was higher when samples were taken using the INBO_0_10 protocol, compared to the LUCAS protocol (with an average difference of 12.4 OTUs (range: 8 to 20)). All protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30 and LUCAS) showed no significant deviation from normality (Shapiro-Wilk test: $p > 0.05$), indicating the data is approximately normal. Non-parametric tests (Friedman test and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests) were however used due to the small sample size ($n \leq 9$) and to ensure robustness against potential violations of assumptions, despite the data being approximately normal. Analysis of observed species richness for Arthropoda across the three sampling protocols showed no significant differences (Friedman test: $\chi^2 = 4.06$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.13$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction revealed a marginally non-significant difference between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS protocols

($p[\text{adj}] = 0.06$), while no significant differences were found between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.22$) or between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.9$). Effect sizes for these comparisons were large for INBO_0_10 vs LUCAS ($d = 1.43$), moderate for INBO_0_10 vs INBO_10_30 ($d = 0.69$), and negligible for INBO_10_30 vs LUCAS ($d = -0.07$). Since the residuals of the paired differences were approximately normal, analysis of observed species richness for Arthropoda across the three sampling protocols was also conducted using paired t-tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction, which revealed a significant difference between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS protocols ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.008$), while no significant differences were found between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.18$) or between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.84$), consistent with the non-parametric results. These results suggest that **depth has a greater effect on Arthropoda richness than sampling intensity**, with the combination of surface sampling and higher subsample number yielding substantially higher richness results.

While the relative species richness is similar between sampling protocols, samples from Seneffe showed an extreme shift in species richness ranking, going from the lowest species richness measured using the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol to the highest with the INBO_10_30 protocol. The highest average rank change was indeed observed between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30 (2.38 positions), followed by INBO_10_30 and LUCAS (1.88 positions), and the lowest average rank change was observed between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS (1.25 positions).

Figure 49. Observed species richness (Inse01 Arthropoda OTUs) based on each sampling protocol, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

In four out of eight locations, the **Shannon diversity** index was higher when samples were collected using the INBO_0_10 protocol compared to the INBO_10_30 protocol (**Fig. 50**). For five locations, the Shannon diversity index was higher for the INBO_0_10 protocol than for LUCAS. Compared to species richness, the Shannon index shows larger rank shifts among sampling protocols. For example, samples from Diepenbeek ranked third using INBO_0_10, but dropped to second lowest when using INBO_10_30, and lowest when using LUCAS. Similarly, Cerfontaine ranked second when using INBO_0_10 but shifted to a low position (sixth) when using both INBO_10_30 and LUCAS. The Shannon index showed larger rank shifts among sampling protocols than species richness, highlighting **the effect of sampling protocol on evaluating trends in diversity**.

Figure 50. Shannon diversity index (based on Inse01 Arthropoda OTUs) across different sampling protocols, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

Figure 51. Observed species richness (*Inse01* Arthropoda OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

With the exception of croplands, species richness and diversity (Shannon) was highest in samples taken using the INBO_0_10 protocol. For forests, this was followed by the LUCAS protocol, and then the INBO_10_30 protocol, while for grasslands and recreation, LUCAS and INBO_10_30 showed comparably (low) values (**Fig. 51**). The same trend was observed for diversity (Shannon index), with the exception of recreational grassland, where all three sampling protocols showed similar values (**Fig. 52**). The **biggest difference between sampling protocols in both richness and diversity was observed in forests**. Based on the INBO_0_10 and LUCAS sampling protocols, **richness and Shannon diversity increased towards the less intensively managed ecosystems**, with the highest values recorded in forests. In contrast, **the INBO_10_30 sampling protocol failed to capture such a pattern**, and richness was similar across all land-use types, and Shannon diversity decreased towards the less intensively managed ecosystems.

Figure 52. Shannon diversity index (based on Inse01 Arthropoda OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

3.4.3.2.5. Effect of sampling protocol on community composition

For Arthropoda, PCoA ordinations based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities computed from CLR-transformed data show that for most locations, INBO_0_10 samples are more similar in community composition to LUCAS samples, than to INBO_10_30 (**Fig. 42**).

3.5. Fungi

3.5.1. General

After quality control and filtering, PacBio Sequel 2 sequencing resulted in a read count per sample varying from 1,856 to 18,110, averaging at 8,228 reads overall. A total of 3348 OTUs were found across 32 samples, and mainly classified as Ascomycota (1560 OTUs), Basidiomycota (568 OTUs), Rozellomycota (322 OTUs), Mortierellomycota (137 OTUs) and Chytridiomycota (127 OTUs), while the remaining 197 OTUs were distributed among several other phyla, including Glomeromycota (56 OTUs), Mucoromycota (51 OTUs) and Zoopagomycota (33 OTUs). Blastocladiomycota, Kickxellomycota, Monoblepharomycota, Basidiobolomycota, GS01, Neocallimastigomycota and Olpidiomycota each represented less than 20 OTUs, while the phyla Aphelidiomycota and Entorrhizomycota were each represented by only one OTU. 437 OTUs (13%) remained unclassified at the phylum level. 1005 (30%) OTUs could be classified at the genus level, of which 505 (15% of total OTUs) could be further identified at the species level (Fig. 53).

After correcting for uneven sequencing depth per sample, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota accounted for 62.7 and 21.5% of the total reads, respectively, followed by Mortierellomycota (8.2%), Rozellomycota (1.8%), and Mucoromycota (1.6%). The other phyla each represented less than 1%, while the OTUs that remained unclassified at the phylum level accounted for 2.9%. *Mortierella*, *Pseudeurotium* and *Russula* were the most abundant genera overall, accounting for 8.03, 6.13, and 4.12% of the total reads, respectively, while the remaining genera consisted of *Cenococcum* (3.91%), *Saitozyma* (3.38%), *Solicoccozyma* (3.12%), *Plectosphaerella* (1.47%), *Gibberella* (1.46%), *Apiotrichum* (1.46%), *Alternaria* (1.28%), *Cortinarius* (1.26%), *Penicillium* (1.15%), *Metarhizium* (1.06%), *Dichotomopilus* (1.06%) and *Penicillium* (1.10%). All the other genera (e.g. Umbelopsis, Inocybe, Exophiala, Amanita and Podospora) each represented less than 1%. Unidentified genera accounted for 41.5% of the total reads, highlighting a substantial portion of the fungal community whose genus could not be determined based on the current sequence reference databases (UNITE).

Pseudeurotium hygrophilum, *Russula anatina* and *Cenococcum geophilum* were the most abundant species overall, accounting for 6.13%, 3.85%, and 3.71% of the total reads, respectively, followed by *Saitozyma podzolica* (3.38%), *Mortierella minutissima* (2.84%), *Solicoccozyma terricola* (1.76%), *Mortierella rishikesha* (1.55%), *Plectosphaerella oratosquillae* (1.47%) and *Alternaria metachromatica* (1.23%). Unidentified species accounted for 49.3% of the total reads.

Nine known species were found across all 11 sampled locations (*Apiotrichum gracile*, *Clonostachys rosea*, *Exophiala equina*, *Mortierella exigua*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Mortierella minutissima*, *Mortierella rishiksha*, *Pseudeurotium hygrophilum* and *Solicoccozyma terricola*).

Figure 53. Krona plot visualizing all Fungi (ITS) taxa detected in this study. Each ring in the plot represents a hierarchical level (kingdom - phylum - class - order - family - genus - species/OTU). The size of the segments reflects the relative read abundance of each taxon across the complete dataset.

3.5.2. Effects of different protocols on taxa detection and diversity

3.5.2.1. Sampling protocol

3.5.2.1.1. Effect of sampling protocol on species detection

In Diepenbeek, the percentage of known species exclusively detected by the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol was higher (37%) than the number of known species detected by all three protocols (25%). At all nine locations, more **species** were **uniquely detected** by at least one of the INBO sampling protocols than by the LUCAS sampling protocol.

All protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30, and LUCAS) show strong deviation from normality (Shapiro-Wilk test: $p < 2.2e-16$ for all). Given this, non-parametric tests (Friedman test for overall differences and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for pairwise comparisons) are used instead of parametric alternatives. Analysis of unique species detection for Fungi across the three sampling protocols showed significant differences (Friedman test: $p = 2.66e-06$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction revealed a **significant** difference **between INBO_0_10 and LUCAS** protocols ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.006$), a **highly significant** difference **between INBO_0_10 and INBO_10_30** ($p[\text{adj}] = 1.45e-06$) and no significant difference between INBO_10_30 and LUCAS ($p[\text{adj}] = 0.2$).

3.5.2.1.2. Unique and shared taxa per sampling protocol

Both LUCAS and INBO protocols uniquely detected certain species across multiple locations, but the INBO protocols did so across a greater number of locations. Species most frequently missed by LUCAS but detected by INBO included *Fusarium venenatum*, *Scutellinia scutellata* and *Arthrographis longispora*, each uniquely detected using the INBO sampling protocol across five locations, while *Mycosphaerella tassiana*, *Solicoccozyma terrea*, *Humicola nigrescens* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were each uniquely detected using the INBO sampling protocol across four locations. In contrast, species that were uniquely detected by LUCAS but missed by INBO across multiple locations, were generally limited to two locations, including *Ganoderma adpersum*, *Vishniacozyma carnescens*, *Mortierella indohii*, *Byssonectria deformis*, *Aspergillus collinsii*, *Periconia cookei*, *Conocybe velutipes* and *Leucosporidium drummii*.

3.5.2.1.3. Forest floor vs mineral soil

When considering all OTUs, the **forest floor sampling protocol** in Diepenbeek **recovered the highest proportion of uniquely detected fungal taxa** among all protocols, with 31% of fungal taxa found exclusively in the forest floor. Additionally, 63% of all fungal taxa were only detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 31% unique to the forest floor, the 21% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10 and 11% detected by both). Both forest floor vs LUCAS and forest floor vs INBO_10_30 shared only 1% of all OTUs. Meanwhile, only 5% of all OTUs were recovered by all three mineral soil sampling protocols, but not by the forest floor sampling protocol. This indicates **substantially different fungal genetic diversity can be recovered in both the forest floor vs mineral soil.**

When considering all OTUs, the forest floor sampling protocol in Gontrode recovered the highest proportion of uniquely detected fungal taxa among all protocols, with **46% of fungal taxa uniquely detected in the forest floor.** Additionally, 69% of all fungal taxa were detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 46% unique to the forest floor, 14% detected by both, and 9% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10). 8% of taxa were uniquely detected by INBO_10_30, indicating equal contribution to unique biodiversity detection for this location when compared to the INBO_0_10 protocol.

When considering only the known species, similar trends were observed. In Diepenbeek, the forest floor sampling protocol recovered the highest amount of unique taxonomic diversity, with 26% of fungal species uniquely detected in the forest floor. Additionally, 64% of all fungal species were only detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 26% unique to the forest floor, the 19% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10 and the 12% detected by both). The forest floor and LUCAS sampling protocols shared no known species, while the forest floor and INBO_10_30 sampling protocols shared only 1% of all known species detected. Only 4% of all known species was recovered by all three mineral soil sampling protocols, but not in the forest floor. Similar to genetic diversity, this indicates **substantially different taxonomic diversity can be recovered in both the forest floor vs mineral soil.**

In Gontrode, the forest floor sampling protocol recovered the highest amount of unique taxonomic diversity, with **39% of fungal species uniquely detected in the forest floor.** Additionally, 58% of all species were detected by the forest floor and/or INBO_0_10 sampling protocols (combining the 39% unique to the forest floor, 15% detected by both, and 4% uniquely detected by INBO_0_10). Interestingly, 20% of all species were shared among all three protocols, while 10% of species were uniquely detected by INBO_10_30, indicating that this layer recovered more unique species than the INBO_0_10 protocol in Gontrode.

3.5.2.1.4. Effect of sampling protocol on species richness and diversity

Figure 54. Observed species richness (Fungi ITS OTUs) based on each sampling protocol, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

The observed species richness and Shannon diversity index of locations differed substantially between sampling protocols. Several shifts in richness and diversity rankings were observed (Fig. 54, 55). Across the sampled locations, no single sampling protocol consistently recovered the highest diversity. In six out of eight locations, observed species richness was higher with the INBO_10_30 protocol than with LUCAS. Additionally, in seven out of nine locations (except for the croplands Bredene and Burdinne), at least one of the INBO protocols recorded higher richness than LUCAS. Samples from the Diepenbeek location showed the most notable change in both observed species richness and Shannon index, going from the highest species richness when using the INBO_0_10 sampling protocol to the lowest when using the INBO_10_30 and LUCAS protocols.

All protocols (INBO_0_10, INBO_10_30 and LUCAS) show no significant deviation from normality (Shapiro-Wilk test: $p > 0.05$), indicating the data is approximately normal (INBO_0_10 $p = 0.6$,

INBO_10_30 $p = 0.38$ and LUCAS $p = 0.63$). Analysis of observed species richness for Fungi across the three sampling protocols revealed no significant differences (Friedman test: $\chi^2 = 1.75$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.42$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction identified no significant differences between any of the protocols. Effect sizes for these comparisons were small for INBO_0_10 vs INBO_10_30 ($d = -0.17$), small to moderate for INBO_0_10 vs LUCAS ($d = 0.32$) and moderate for INBO_10_30 vs LUCAS ($d = 0.57$).

Figure 55. Shannon diversity index (based on Fungi ITS OTUs) across different sampling protocols, with samples from the same plot connected by coloured lines.

Figure 56. Observed species richness (Fungi ITS OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

The **largest differences in Fungi richness between sampling protocols were found in forests**, where the INBO_0_10 protocol recorded nearly twice the richness of LUCAS (**Fig. 56**). This was followed by a park in Molenbeek, where INBO_10_30 reported the highest species richness. In contrast, croplands and grasslands showed minimal differences in observed richness among sampling protocols. Similar patterns were observed for the Shannon diversity index (**Fig. 57**).

Figure 57. Shannon diversity index (based on Fungi ITS OTUs) across different land-use categories, with mean values represented by points. Colors indicate the sampling protocols used.

3.5.2.1.5. Effect of sampling protocol on community composition

PCoA ordinations based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity computed from CLR-transformed and rarefied data, show that most samples from the same location, but taken using a different sampling protocol, cluster together (**Fig. 58**), and thus are similar in community composition.

Figure 58. PCoA plot of Fungi (ITS) based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities calculated from CLR-transformed community data, with colors representing locations and shapes indicating different sampling protocols.

4. Discussion

As future soil biodiversity monitoring programmes will likely rely mostly on molecular methods due to the huge effort and cost of traditional methods, the use of eDNA for monitoring soil invertebrates needs to be refined. The following problems were identified in this study and need to be addressed:

- Primer development: The universal Eukaryotic 18S primers used by LUCAS, BiodivERsA+ soil pilot and SoilBON (Guerra *et al.*, 2021) to target all Eukaryotes lacked sufficient taxonomic resolution and showed amplification bias towards protists, with limited biodiversity recovery for soil invertebrate groups such as earthworms, potworms, and springtails. The use of more targeted primers drastically improved amplification and taxonomic resolution of these important soil taxa. This was also found in previous studies (Ficetola & Taberlet, 2022; Giebner *et al.*, 2020; Jurburg *et al.*, 2021; Kirse *et al.*, 2021). A possible solution to the primer problem is thus the use of multiple group-specific primers, as shown in this study. Interestingly, newly developed primers have been shown to perform equally well for both soil Annelida and Arthropoda, including Collembola (Terr_EPTDr2n; Perrelet *et al.*, unpublished; Lambrechts *et al.*, unpublished).
- Another issue is the quantity of soil used for DNA-extraction. Although in this study only tested on the universal Eukaryotic 18S primers, and not on the group-specific invertebrate primers, 30 additional genera across Collembola, Annelida, and Arthropoda were detected using the phosphate buffer method. This suggests using DNA-extraction methods that start with a larger amount of material (soil) significantly increases the taxonomic diversity that can be detected. Following the LUCAS protocol for DNA-extraction, 0.25 g of soil is used, which is relevant for microorganisms, but does not seem representative enough for meso- and macrofauna, where at least 15 g is needed. This has also been shown in previous studies (Dopheide *et al.*, 2019; Taberlet *et al.*, 2012b).
- The depth of the sampled soil layer significantly influenced species detection. Our results show that the upper soil layer (0–10 cm) yields a significantly higher number of species, while the diversity of taxa and eDNA in the deeper 10–30 cm soil layer seems rather limited for annelids and arthropods to reliably serve as soil health indicators or for demonstrating ecological changes. Indeed, many species were detected exclusively by INBO_0_10 and/or LUCAS, while

very few were exclusively recorded using INBO_10_30, suggesting that the deeper 10-30 cm soil layer provides little additional value for detecting annelids and arthropods based on eDNA. Moreover, it has been previously hypothesized that deeper soil layers contain more relic DNA and dead organisms (necromass), inherited from former times, potentially obscuring diversity estimates (Carini *et al.*, 2016; Köninger *et al.*, 2023). Based on these findings, we propose that the 0–10 cm layer provides a more recent and ecologically relevant eDNA signal, making it better suited for establishing and applying soil biodiversity indicators. Additionally, the forest floor layer showed potential for monitoring soil biodiversity through metabarcoding, consistent with previous studies (Ruppert *et al.*, 2023; Zinger *et al.*, 2019).

- Sampling intensity and sampling area: Our results suggest that we are able to detect more species when more subsamples are taken over a larger area to make the composite soil sample. Detecting a greater number of species provides a larger, more robust, and more representative dataset, which improves the ability to identify ecological patterns and trends. With a limited number of detected species, accurately discerning such patterns becomes statistically more challenging. Such improved sampling protocols that reduce, as much as possible, the influence of local spatial heterogeneity by mixing a larger amount of subsamples over a larger area than currently prescribed in the LUCAS protocol, have previously been designed (e.g. Taberlet *et al.*, 2012b) and, to a limited extent, adopted in e.g. SoilBON Field sampling protocol v1.6 (Potapov *et al.*, 2022).
- Reference databases: Incomplete publicly available taxonomic reference databases currently limit the potential of eDNA metabarcoding (Blackman *et al.*, 2024; Taberlet *et al.*, 2012a). Several examples of this problem were encountered in this study: (1) Numerous Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) identified as belonging to the *Aporrectodea* genus could not be conclusively assigned to specific species, as they exhibit a high degree of phylogenetic similarity in terms of sequence homology to several distinct *Aporrectodea* species. However, this might also be in part due to potential mislabeling of several *Aporrectodea* sequences within the NCBI and EMBL sequence reference databases. For instance, several OTUs share more than 99% sequence similarity with both *Aporrectodea caliginosa* and *Aporrectodea tuberculata*. This complicates accurate taxonomic classification of the OTUs, and highlights the need for more precise and

consistent taxonomic reference data in the databases. (2) Because of incomplete sequence reference databases, and varying intra- and interspecific sequence similarity cutoffs for different species and genera which are oftentimes still unknown, several of the unclassified OTUs in this study (such as for example *Fridericia_otu662*) might actually represent known species, which complicates the comparison of detection of known species between sampling protocols. (3) After performing parallel taxonomic assignments of 18S ASVs, using both the database LUCAS used (SILVA), and the PR2 reference database, our study revealed consistently higher taxonomic resolution with the PR2 database for both Annelida and Collembola. The PR2 database resolved 11 unique genera for Annelida and 16 for Collembola, whereas the SILVA database failed to provide genus-level resolution, only assigning ASVs to higher taxonomic levels (phylum and class). (4) Despite PR2's recent update to a standardized nine-rank taxonomy, key taxonomic levels are still missing for certain groups. For example, arthropods lack order- and family-level information, while annelids lack class-, order- and family-level information. These gaps reduce compatibility and highlight the need for more complete and consistent reference databases for accurate biodiversity assessments.

It should be noted that, in general, due to the limitations outlined above, the reliability of taxonomic assignments below the order or family level remains uncertain. For more accurate species-level identification, a reference barcode database specific to national communities should be established and used either independently or in combination with publicly available databases, to maximize both the reliability and the number of taxa assignments. Increased investment in standardized barcoding initiatives to build comprehensive reference databases is critical to unlocking the full capability of eDNA metabarcoding for soil biodiversity monitoring. It should be noted that with major initiatives, such as the International Barcode of Life project, or the Earth BioGenome project underway, the development and expansion of such reference databases is very likely (Blackman *et al.*, 2024).

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of eDNA metabarcoding as an effective tool for monitoring soil biodiversity and shows that sampling and molecular protocols need and can be optimized for important soil invertebrate groups (Annelida, Collembola, Arthropoda). Our findings suggest that sampling and sequencing of surface layers (0–10 cm and forest floor) separately detects a greater diversity of soil-dwelling, soil-surface, and soil-associated invertebrates, while deeper layers (10–30 cm) contribute little to the eDNA-based detection of these groups. Collecting a greater number of subsamples over a larger area to create the composite soil sample, along with using larger soil volumes for DNA extraction, improves the biodiversity recovery of these groups and supports more robust ecological analyses. Additionally, targeted primer sets for key soil invertebrate groups are necessary to improve taxonomic resolution and facilitate the development of policy-relevant soil health indicators. Integrating these refinements into standardized protocols, such as LUCAS, will strengthen soil biodiversity monitoring and enable more effective conservation and land management strategies across Europe.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and analyzed for this study are available on Zenodo under the title "Data from: Comparison and evaluation of sampling and eDNA metabarcoding protocols to assess soil biodiversity in Belgian LUCAS Biopoints." This dataset includes interactive Krona taxonomy charts to visually summarize the diversity and relative read abundance of detected taxa across sampled locations, sampling protocols tested, and primer sets tested. The Zenodo repository can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14845588>. Raw sequencing data will be published on Zenodo and deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) or GenBank upon publication of the findings in a peer-reviewed academic journal. Supplementary information is available in a separate document titled "Comparison and evaluation of sampling and eDNA metabarcoding protocols to assess soil biodiversity in Belgian LUCAS Biopoints: Supplementary Information."

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